

**Hipparcos:
Scientific objectives, principle of observation,
and accuracy analysis
(October 1979)**

The following 73 pages constituted my input to the ESA document *Hipparcos Spacecraft Design and Development* (PF616, 5 December 1979) summarizing the results of in-house (ESTEC/ESOC) studies of the Hipparcos mission performed in 1978–1979. These studies were made following the publication of the "red brochure" DP/PS(78)13 in April 1978 and its favourable review by the ESA advisory committees. The PF616 report provided the technical basis for the selection of the Hipparcos mission in February 1980.

My contribution was written while I was a research fellow at ESTEC in February to October 1979.

2.1. Scientific objectives and principles of observation

2.1.1. Scientific objectives

The space astrometry mission HIPPARCOS aims at measuring with unprecedented accuracy the trigonometric parallaxes, proper motions, and positions of about 100 000 selected stars, most of them brighter than magnitude 10. The expected average imprecision is in the range 1 - 2 marcsec ($0''.001 - 0''.002$) for the parallaxes and in each coordinate of the positions and proper motions per year.

Such an order-of-magnitude improvement in precision and number of data, as compared with the present and near future situation, can only be obtained with a dedicated astrometric instrument operating in space and taking advantage of zero gravity, full sky visibility, constant thermal environment, and absence of a refracting atmosphere.

Cost considerations and technological constraints on the other hand necessarily limit the size of such an instrument so that only relatively bright stars can be observed, although in great number. HIPPARCOS is thus complementary to other optical astrometric programmes for the coming decade, notably the astrometric use of Space Telescope /1/,^{*} optical interferometry /2, 3/, and new developments of traditional narrow-field astrometry /4/, which all aim at a similar (or even better) precision but are limited to a small number of generally fainter stars. Compared with all other techniques HIPPARCOS possesses however two absolutely unique capabilities: to measure absolute parallaxes and, to build a rigid and consistent system of positions and proper motions over the entire celestial sphere.

A successful space astrometry mission will have direct or indirect impact on almost every branch of astronomy. Its scientific significance has been summarized in the Space Astrometry Phase A Report /5/ and further elaborated in several papers presented at a Colloquium on European Satellite Astrometry held in Padova, Italy, in June 1978 /6/.

*References to Section 2.1. are listed at the end of Chapter 3.

2.1.2. General principles

The basic principle of observation is to scan continuously and systematically the entire sky with a telescope capable of accurately measuring the angles between stars separated by a large angle, approximately 69° . By numerically combining several millions of such angle measurements collected over a time span of a few years, it is possible to derive the astrometric parameters (i.e. the parallax and the components of the position and proper motion) of each star. The angles are measured by superimposing in the focal plane of a single telescope two fields of view, 69° apart on the sky, each field containing one of the stars in a pair. The angle (γ) between the two fields of view is maintained by a complex mirror in front of the telescope, splitting its entrance pupil into two equal parts and directing the light from one star into one half of the entrance pupil and that from the other star into the other half. The scanning motion causes the star images to travel across the focal plane of the telescope, in which there is a system of slits (grid) and, behind this, a photon counting detector. The photon counts are transmitted to the ground and processed to yield the times at which the star images crossed the different slits, and hence the relative positions of the stars in the combined field of view. The true angle between two stars belonging to different fields of view is obtained by adding the basic angle γ to the apparent angle in the combined field of view.

2.1.3. Scanning law

Thanks to the beam-splitting complex mirror, there are effectively two optical axes, making an angle $\gamma \approx 69^\circ$ to each other, and defining a principal plane in which, ideally, all angle measurements take place. The instrument (and the satellite as a whole) spins around an axis nominally normal to this plane, at a rate of about ten turns per day; consequently, the two fields of view scan within a few hours a strip of the sky along a great circle in the principal plane. The width of the strip is about one degree, as set by the width of the fields of view. In the course of one great-circle scan each star in the strip is seen twice by the telescope, as it enters both fields of view with half an hour delay.

In order to successively cover the whole celestial sphere it is however necessary to change the direction of the spin axis, continuously or in small steps, in such a way that consecutively scanned strips overlap by half their width. The scanning law, i.e. the path on the sky described by the nominal spin axis ($\hat{z}$), must enable sufficiently frequent observations of each star, with scans intersecting at sufficient angles for determination of both coordinates, and with non-zero and different parallax factors. At the same time it must comply with power requirements in particular, which effectively constrain the angle of $\hat{z}$ from the sun to less than about 40° , since $\hat{z}$ is also the normal to the plane of the solar arrays.

This is achieved with a revolving scanning law according to which the spin axis constantly points as far away from the sun as possible, and performs a circular motion around the sun with at least $270^\circ/\xi$ full revolutions around the sun per year, ξ being the constant angle between $\hat{z}$ and the sun. This law guarantees that a particular star is observed in at least 12 great-circle scans per year (the average number is 28 scans per year) and results in a reasonably uniform accuracy of the astrometric parameters for different stars. The desire to keep the angle ξ as large as possible follows from the fact that the parallax factor of any star at any time, and hence the accuracy of derived parallaxes, is directly proportional to $\sin \xi$.

2.1.4. Grid and detection system

The grid consists of a few thousand parallel slits, covering most of the combined field of view at highly regular intervals of about one arcs. The slits are normal to the principal plane and hence to the apparent motion of the stars produced by the spin. For each star the light transmitted by the grid will consist of a train of light pulses, each pulse corresponding to one slit; the detector converts the pulses into a sequence of photon counts from which the timing of the different pulses or, equivalently, the phase of the entire pulse train can be derived.

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The apparent angle between two stars in the combined field of view is obtained as the phase difference between the corresponding pulse trains times a scale factor depending on the linear separation of slits (grid period) and the equivalent focal length of the telescope. Inasmuch as the phases can be determined strictly simultaneously, any irregularity of spin affects both phases equally and introduces no error in the angle measurement. The desired accuracy can thus be reached without seriously relying on either absolute pointing accuracy or smoothness of motion.

The detector is a photon-counting image dissector tube having an instantaneous field of view (IFOV) approximately 30" in diameter. This can be electronically directed to any position within the one degree combined field of view. Compared with a conventional photomultiplier tube integrating over the whole field of view this offers two decisive advantages. Firstly, it reduces background light roughly by a factor 10^{-4} , thereby enabling observation of stars about four magnitudes fainter. Secondly, it removes the confusion that would result from superimposing the pulse trains of all the stars in the field, since the IFOV will in general contain only one star at a time.

However, it also adds complexity. In order to direct the IFOV to the correct position and properly follow a star image across the field of view, the celestial coordinates of the star and the three-axes attitude of the instrument must be known in real time to within a few arcs. Star coordinates are up-linked from the ground, but the attitude determination for this purpose must be performed on board, using gyros and observations with a star mapper.

Furthermore, with the image dissector tube it is no longer possible to obtain strictly simultaneous observations of several stars. Attitude irregularities will consequently introduce small errors into the angle measurements. These are however reduced to a negligible level by switching the IFOV rapidly between the different programme stars in the combined field of view in such a way that it periodically returns to a particular star several times per second.

The star mapper used for attitude determination employs a few slits of different inclinations at the edge of the combined field of view, whereby both coordinates of a star in the field can be obtained. Observation of one star from each field of view determines the three-axes attitude unambiguously and with a precision generally limited by the uncertainty of the celestial coordinates of the stars, i.e. about 0.5 arcs.

2.1.5. Processing of scientific data

The goal of the scientific processing is to transform the photon counts transmitted from the satellite to the ground, roughly 10^{12} bits, into a comprehensible catalogue of astrometric data, containing around 10^7 bits of information.

As an intermediate to the determination of the astrometric parameters of the stars, a large number of parameters describing the instrument and its motion must be derived from the observations. The instrumental parameters include the basic angle, scale value at the grid, orientation and tilt of the grid, and the effective distortion of the grid system, whether coming from grid imperfections or optical distortion. All of them are of course functions of time; while some of them can be regarded as constant throughout the mission, the most critical ones will be calibrated on a short time scale. The basic angle and scale value, in particular, can be obtained with a time resolution equal to the spin period (2.4 hours), since they both follow from the condition that the angles measured along a closed great-circle scan must add up to 360° .

The three-axes attitude motion of the instrument must be derived a posteriori to within $0".1$. This is a consequence of the finite number of stars and the width of the field of view ($\sim 1^\circ$). Since the arc joining the two stars in a pair to be observed is generally slightly inclined to the principal plane, typically by 0.5° , a transformation from measured

angle in the principal plane to the true angle along the arc is required, involving a projection factor $\sim \cos 0.5^\circ$. Consequently, in order to have 0."001 precision after transformation, the inclination must be known to $0."001/\sin 0.5^\circ \simeq 0."1$. In practice this amounts to measuring the coordinate perpendicular to the scan of a number of stars in the field of view, which can be done with the star mapper. An iterative procedure is obviously called for, since the a priori precision of star positions is insufficient for this purpose.

Even though all such auxiliary parameters are successively eliminated in the process of reductions, the astrometric parameters themselves are too many to be solved by any direct method. Fortunately, there are indirect ways to cope with the problem; one is the decomposition in three steps previously described /5, p. 34/. An appealing variant of this is first to solve the astrometric parameters of a kernel of about 1000 stars (the primary system) by means of a direct least-squares solution. The input for this solution are the angles between pairs of primary stars linked together by the other stars, since the sparseness of the primary system generally prevents direct observation of such angles. Once the primary system has been resolved, the backward solution to get the astrometric parameters of the remaining stars is comparatively simple. The whole procedure must be iterated a few times, partly because of the weak non-linearity of the observation equations, but also in order to detect and eliminate errors of observation and effects caused by the duplicity of many stars.

The strictly differential character of observations, and particularly the concept of angle measurements in pairs, has been stressed in the above description of the basic principles of observation. In practice a more general approach is preferred, by considering as the elementary observation not the angle between two stars but the direction of a star referred to the modelised attitude at a certain instant. Measurement of pairs is a special case of this, namely when only directions referred to the same instant of time are compared; attitude modelisation errors are then obviously quite unimportant. If however perturbing torques are sufficiently small and well modelised, it will be possible

to compare also directions obtained some time apart. This will tend to strengthen the solution and reduce the imprecision of estimated directions. This will be the case especially if accurate modelisation is possible over a few minutes of time, i.e. much longer than the 20 seconds it takes a star to cross the field of view, since brighter stars can then be linked together by the attitude model rather than by intermediate fainter stars (dynamical smoothing). In principle, this may substantially improve the accuracy of the astrometric data for the brighter stars, but has little effect on the majority of fainter stars. Again we must emphasize, however, that the expected accuracy of 1 - 2 marcs for the final results can be achieved without an accurate modelisation of the attitude.

3.2. Scanning laws

The scanning motion of the instrument is defined by the paths on the sky described by the two telescope axes, i.e. in the ecliptical coordinate system $[\beta_p(t), \lambda_p(t)]$ and $[\beta_f(t), \lambda_f(t)]$ for the preceding and following axis, respectively. This motion results from the combination of two independent motions:

- (1) a spinning motion at a nominally constant rate around the z axis (normal to the two optical axes), and
- (2) a stepwise or continuous change of the direction of the nominal spin axis (z) according to a predefined scanning law $[\beta_z(t), \lambda_z(t)]$.

The spinning motion is fully determined by the spin rate ω_z or the number of revolutions per day R ($\omega_z = 2\pi R/86400 \text{ rad s}^{-1}$).

With respect to the sun $[0, \lambda_{\odot}(t)]$ the scanning law may alternatively be specified by the angles $\xi(t)$ and $\nu(t)$ (Fig. 3.2.1) according to the equations

$$\beta_z(t) = \arcsin[\sin \xi(t) \sin \nu(t)], \quad (3.2.1)$$

$$\lambda_z(t) = \lambda_{\odot}(t) + \arcsin[\sin \xi(t) \cos \nu(t) / \cos \beta_z(t)].$$

It has been decided that the most satisfactory scanning law, from several points of view, is a revolving scanning defined by $\xi(t) = \text{constant}$ and $\nu(t)$ increasing (or decreasing) at an almost constant rate. In the simplest case $\nu(t)$ is a linear function of t or $\lambda_{\odot}$; however, it has been shown that it is possible to achieve that the speed of z along its path on the sky is nearly or perfectly constant, by introducing a slight modulation of the rate $\dot{\nu}(t)$ (uniform revolving scanning, /15, 17/). Irrespective of the detailed form of $\nu(t)$ it is found that the main characteristics of the scanning law are the sun angle ξ and the average number of revolutions of z around the sun per year, $K = \langle \dot{\nu}(t) / \dot{\lambda}_{\odot}(t) \rangle$.

Optimisation of the scanning motion is thus essentially the selection of ξ , K, and R while taking into account a number of considerations and (sometimes) conflicting requirements. We shall briefly discuss some of the more important aspects on this optimisation, viz.

a. technical and mission analysis aspects, e.g.

- electrical power requirements;
- straylight elimination (baffles design);
- minimum manoeuvring and simplicity of operation;
- acceptable data rates and computer load;

b. scientific aspects, e.g.

- theoretical observability of all astrometric parameters;
- optimisation of global precision;
- full sky coverage and reasonably uniform precision;
- uniform distribution of observation epochs for any given star;
- redundancy of observations;
- overlap of successive great-circle scans;
- intricacy of observation pattern;
- minimum interruptions and dead time by earth and moon occultations.

3.2.1. Technical aspects

Although we are here mainly concerned with the scientific aspects of the mission, a short recollection of the technical constraints is motivated. The selected configuration of solar panels in one plane, normal to the z axis, implies that the available electric power is roughly proportional to $\cos \xi$. Steerable solar panels would not only be a major technical complication but would interfere unacceptably with observations. In practice the imposed limit on ξ for this reason is of the order of 45° . A similar constraint results from the baffles. To avoid excessive straylight from the sun, it is required

that no direct sunlight hits the internal walls of the baffles. This is achieved by canting their exit planes an angle slightly greater than ξ . With increasing canting angle the baffles become however less efficient in reducing straylight from other sources (mainly the earth and moon), leading to more frequent interruptions of scans and increased observation dead time. This might be compensated by making the baffles longer; but since their overall length (from complex mirror surfaces to the top of the exit plane) is limited to about 1.5 m, the maximum practicable canting angle seems to be about 45° .

The nominally constant spin rate and slow precessional motion of the spin axis cause no manoeuvring problems, since the main effort of the attitude control goes into counteracting perturbing torques.

Constraints on data rates and on-board computer load (mainly IDT piloting) impose limits on the spin rate. The present baseline $R = 10 \text{ rev day}^{-1}$ is acceptable, but twice this rate would probably create problems.

3.2.2. Scientific aspects: sky coverage and redundancy

Consider the revolving scanning law depicted in Fig. 3.2.2. The path of the spin axis (zz') consists of slightly overlapping loops. A star at P may be observed whenever the angle from P to z is nearly 90° , i.e. when z is at z_1 , z_2 , or z_3 , at the intersections with a great circle with its pole at P. It is easy to see that there are at least six such intersections per year, irrespective of the position of the star. Thus, thanks to the slightly overlapping loops, there may be at least six observations of every star per year, or 15 observations in 2.5 years, which guarantees a full sky coverage. The condition for overlapping loops is

$$|K| \geq 270^\circ/\xi. \quad (3.2.2)$$

If this is not satisfied there will be certain areas on the sky observable only twice per year (Fig. 3.2.3) or 5 times in 2.5 years, which means that there is practically no redundancy at

all, since there are five astrometric parameters per star to be determined. On the other hand, there is little point in having K much greater than $270^\circ/\xi$ unless one goes to $K = 450^\circ/\xi$, which would make it possible to observe each star at least ten times per year (Fig. 3.2.4).

The sky coverage and distribution of observing time on various parts of the sky have also been extensively studied by means of numerical experiments /19, 20/, which in particular have confirmed the full coverage obtained with scanning laws satisfying (3.2.2). They have also shown, however, that the coverage is far from uniform; in particular the higher latitudes $|\beta| \geq 90^\circ - \xi$ are strongly oversampled. This again can be understood by making reference to Fig. 3.2.2. If the latitude of P is more than $90^\circ - \xi$, the great circle will cut through all K loops (per year), so that there may be $2K \geq 540^\circ/\xi$ observation epochs per year at such latitudes. The non-uniformity should decrease with increasing ξ , as has indeed been shown by the numerical experiments /19/.

The above reasoning presumes that the spin rate is sufficient for a certain overlap of successively scanned strips along the great circles, so that a star cannot slip away between two successive scans. Since the average speed of z along its path is $[1 + (K^2 - \frac{1}{2}) \sin^2 \xi]^{\frac{1}{2}} 360^\circ \text{ yr}^{-1}$, while the width of the FOV is 0.9° , we obtain the criterion

$$|R| > 1.1 [1 + (K^2 - \frac{1}{2}) \sin^2 \xi]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (3.2.3)$$

Combined with (3.2.2) this gives $|R| \geq 5$, almost independent of ξ . Selecting $R = 10$ gives overlap by half the field width at the anti-nodes and hence sufficient margin for excursions of the actual attitude motion from the nominal.

The $K = 450^\circ/\xi$ law requires $|R| \geq 8$, which is still compatible with the baseline value $R = 10$, but the overlap at the anti-nodes reduces to 20 %.

3.2.3. Theoretical observability and global precision

The basic principle of observation is one-dimensional, i.e. to measure instantaneous relative positions of stars along the scanning great circles. Only parameters producing measurable relative displacements along the scan are thus theoretically observable; in addition, since all five astrometric parameters of a particular star combine to produce a certain displacement at the instant of observation, that star has to be observed at least five times at which the parameters combine in distinctly different ways. The theoretical observability of all five astrometric parameters of a star at any point on the sky has been thoroughly demonstrated, for revolving scanning laws obeying (3.2.2), by numerical experiments /19/. These have also shown most clearly how the precision of the different parameters depends on ξ and the position of the star. Some simple considerations of the basic scanning geometry are nevertheless helpful for a good understanding of the problem.

Consider again the revolving scanning law shown in Fig. 3.2.2, and let us for a moment forget about the proper motion and parallax of the star P. The possibility to determine both latitude and longitude of P depends on whether the different scans across P intersect at a sufficient angle. At the time when the spin axis is at z_1 there will be a scan across P in a direction perpendicular to z_1P . At some later times there will be scans perpendicular to z_2P and z_3P . The first two scans intersect at an angle $u = z_1Pz_2$. It is easily seen, since the latitude of z varies between $\pm \xi$, that there will always be at least one pair of scans intersecting at $u \approx 2\xi$, whatever may be the position of the star. A necessary condition for theoretical observability of positions is then $\xi \neq 0$. The most isotropic precision (equal precisions in β and λ , or rather zero eccentricity of error ellipse) is obviously obtained with scans intersecting at right angles, which is approximately realised with $\xi = 45^\circ$. In the absence of proper motions and parallaxes half a year of observations would be sufficient to get good positions over the whole sky.

Now let us turn to the proper motions. The three scans across P corresponding to z_1 , z_2 , and z_3 are too close in time (especially if ξ is small) and too few to determine both the position and proper motion of P (at least four scans are needed). However, there will be another set of (at least) three scans across P roughly half a year later, when the path of z cuts the great circle of P on the opposite side of the sphere. Thus, in the absence of parallaxes, observations over one year are sufficient to separate positions and proper motions of all stars.

Consider finally the parallax observability (Fig. 3.2.5). The parallactic displacement of the apparent position of a star P is always in the direction of the sun and amounts to $d = \varpi \sin \theta$, where ϖ is the parallax and θ the angle between P and S (the sun). However, only the component of d along the scan is observable with HIPPARCOS, viz. $d_{\parallel} = -d \sin a$, where a is the angle SPz. But from the sine theorem $\sin a \sin \theta = \sin \xi \sin w$; hence

$$d_{\parallel} = -\varpi \sin \xi \sin w. \quad (3.2.4)$$

Necessary conditions for parallax observability are then that $\xi \neq 0$ and that the angle w is different at the different observation epochs. That the latter condition is fulfilled with the revolving scanning law can be seen from Fig. 3.2.2. The possibility of disentangling the parallax from the position and proper motion has been demonstrated by numerical experiments; at least 1.5 years observation is needed for a good separation of the five parameters, although a non-singular solution is obtained already with one year, which is however the absolute minimum mission length for getting useful results.

According to 3.2.4 the mean errors of the parallaxes will be proportional to $(\sin \xi)^{-1}$.

The precision of the astrometric parameters will vary considerably between different parts of the sky /19/. There is in particular a strong variation with latitude of the

precision of the longitude, proper motion in longitude, and parallax. The precision generally increases towards the ecliptical poles, which depends partly on geometrical factors and partly on the oversampling of high latitudes. This inhomogeneity becomes however less pronounced with increasing sun angle ξ . Considering all five parameters together, it appears that the overall astrometric precision is optimised with a sun angle not less than $\xi = 45^\circ$.

The desirability of intricate observation patterns, i.e. maximum variability of the combination of observation factors between the different observation instances of a particular star, is a consequence of the general philosophy that any irregularity is more likely to be detected if subjected to a great variety of conditions. This aspect is particularly important for the detection and proper measurement of double and multiple stars and means, for instance, that a star should be scanned at as many distinctly different position angles as possible throughout the mission /10/. (The position angle of a scan, ψ in Fig. 3.2.5, is the deviation of the scanning direction from the local ecliptical north.) This implies that the scanning law should not be exactly reproduced from one year to the next, i.e. K should be a non-integer. From this point of view the symmetric scanning /15/ is particularly unsuitable.

3.2.4. Earth and moon occultations

For the purpose of the present discussion an earth (or moon) occultation is defined as 'the time interval when the direct or diffused light of the earth (moon) in either FOV is strong enough to prevent or seriously impair scientific observations. Apart from possible thermal impact on the optics, occultations will cause a certain loss of observing time and interruption of scans, with some repercussion on the final astrometric accuracy. The frequency of occultations may be described by two dimensionless numbers: f_1 = fraction of scans interrupted and f_2 = fraction of total observing time lost. The observing time lost (dead time) will simply increase the overall mean

Figure 3.2.3. Revolving scanning with $K < 270^\circ/\xi$.

Figure 3.2.4. Revolving scanning with $K = 450^\circ/\xi$.

Figure 3.2.5. Parallactic displacement of star P is along the great circle joining P and the sun (S). The total displacement is $d = \varpi \sin \theta$, where ϖ is the parallax. The component along the scan is $d_{\parallel} = -d \sin a = -\varpi \sin \xi \sin w$. ψ is the position angle of the scan.

errors with a factor $(1 - f_2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, whereas the effects of the interrupted scans are more difficult to evaluate and may be potentially more dangerous. This is related to the stability and calibration of the basic angle: a good calibration of the basic angle requires an uninterrupted (complete 360°) scan. If the basic angle is sufficiently stable, or its variation is smooth over several hours (making interpolation meaningful), then even a high frequency of interruptions, say $f_1 = 0.5$, would have no appreciable effect on the accuracy.

The preliminary study of the baffles from the Phase A Study /18, I-4.2.2/ indicates that the straylight level is acceptable (less than what corresponds to one 11th magnitude star in the IFOV) as long as no direct earthlight (moonlight) hits the optical surfaces of the complex mirror. The complex mirror and the opening and length of the baffles thus define the two "extended fields of view" into which the illuminated parts of the earth and moon should not enter /21/. With entrance pupil diameter $D = 0.25$ m and baffle length $L = 1.5$ m, the half-width of the extended field of view is of the order of $\tau = \arctan \frac{D}{L} \approx 10^\circ$.

Vaghi has performed a number of simulation experiments to estimate the losses f_1 and f_2 under a variety of conditions. Some of his results are summarised in Table 3.2.1. The main conclusion is that f_1 and f_2 are largely determined by the size of the extended field of view (assumed to be circular in these experiments), but practically independent of the orbital inclination ($i = 0^\circ$ or 23.5°) and scanning law ($\xi = 30^\circ$ or 36° , $K = 270^\circ/\xi$ or $360^\circ/\xi$, and various initial conditions). For the baseline mission ($i = 0^\circ$, $\xi = 36^\circ$, $\tau = 10^\circ$) one deduces the fairly satisfactory $f_1 = 0.31$ and $f_2 = 0.042$.

However, it was pointed out by Höpfg /16/ that the two-split rectangular entrance pupil later adopted as the baseline (0.25×0.10 m²) should be equipped with baffles having rectangular openings, roughly 0.30×0.15 m² normal to the axes, that the extended fields of view are consequently rectangular (half-widths τ_y and τ_z), and that the average dead time and rate of interruptions can be derived by simple statistical

arguments. The following is a slight refinement of Høg's reasoning.

Let j be the inclination of a scan to the orbit of the earth, as seen from the satellite. The scan is interrupted by an earth occultation if, at the right moment, the right ascension of the earth centre happens to be in one of two opposite intervals, each of length $2(\tau_z + \rho)/\sin j$, where ρ is the angular radius of the earth. This is valid provided j is not too far from $\pm 90^\circ$. The fraction of interrupted scans is simply the probability of interruption, i.e. $[4(\tau_z + \rho)\langle 1/\sin j \rangle]/360^\circ$. Since the inclination is $|j| = 90^\circ \pm \xi \pm (23.5^\circ - i)$, we find approximately

$$f_1 = \left[1 + \frac{3}{8} \sin^2 \xi + \frac{3}{8} \sin^2 (23.5^\circ - i) \right] \frac{\tau_z + \rho}{90^\circ}. \quad (3.2.5)$$

The fractional dead time is the product of f_1 and the fraction of the interrupted scan covered by the extended fields of view:

$$f_2 = \left[1 + \frac{3}{8} \sin^2 \xi + \frac{3}{8} \sin^2 (23.5^\circ - i) \right] \frac{(\tau_z + \rho)(\tau_y + \rho)}{90^\circ \cdot 90^\circ}. \quad (3.2.6)$$

If the extended fields are elliptical with semi-axes τ_y and τ_z , the expression for f_2 should be multiplied by $\pi/4$.

Eqs. (3.2.5) - (3.2.6) are compared with Vaghi's computations in the upper half of Table 3.2.1. It is found that the values for f_1 from (3.2.5) should be increased by about 16 %, while (3.2.6) is in excellent agreement with the numerical results.

The lower half of Table 3.2.1 gives the results according to (3.2.5) - (3.2.6) for the rectangular pupil, sun angle 36° and 45° , and rectangular ($0.30 \times 0.15 \text{ m}^2$) and circular (0.335 m diameter) baffle openings. For the baseline configuration the combined effects of earth and moon occultations are:

- fraction of scans interrupted $f_1 = 0.27$
- fractional dead time $f_2 = 0.05,$

which appears to be quite acceptable.

3.2.5. Conclusions

A satisfactory scanning of the whole sky is obtained with a revolving scanning motion characterised by the following parameters:

sun angle: $30^\circ \lesssim \xi \lesssim 45^\circ$ ($\xi = 45^\circ$ preferred)
revolving speed: K non-integer satisfying $|K| \geq 270^\circ/\xi$
spin rate: $|R| \sim 10$.

The advantages of a larger sun angle are:

- improved overall precision, especially for parallaxes;
- more uniform precision at different latitudes;
- less anisotropy of precision (latitude vs. longitude);
- more uniform distribution of observation epochs;
- improved ability to cope with double stars.

The disadvantages are:

- less power available;
- increased observation dead time and scan interruptions by earth and moon occultations;
- increased amplitude of thermal variations due to varying solar aspect angles.

Table 3.2.1. Fraction of interrupted scans (f_1) and fractional dead time (f_2) due to earth and moon occultations, according to numerical experiments (Vaghi, /21/) and eqs. (3.2.5) - (3.2.6).
R/C = rectangular or circular extended fields of view.

i	ξ	τ_y	τ_z	R/C	f_1 (Vaghi)	f_2	f_1 (3.2.5) - (3.2.6)	f_2 (3.2.5) - (3.2.6)
earth occultations ($\rho = 9^\circ$):								
0°	30°	16°	16°	C	37%	7.0%	32%	7.0 ⁺ %
0	30	10	10	C	29	4.0	24	4.0 ⁺
0	30	1	1	C	14	1.0	13	1.1 ⁺
23.5	30	16	16	C	35.5	6.5	30	6.6 ⁺
23.5	30	10	10	C	27	3.8	23	3.8 ⁺
23.5	30	1	1	C	13.5	1.0	12	1.1 ⁺
0	36	16	16	C	38.5	7.3	33	7.2 ⁺
0	36	11.0	5.0	R	-	-	21 ^x	4.1
0	45	11.4	5.2	R	-	-	23 ^x	4.5
0	36	12.1	12.1	C	-	-	32 ^x	5.1 ⁺
moon occultations ($\rho = 0.25^\circ$):								
0	36	11.0	5.0	R	-	-	8 ^x	0.9
earth + moon occultations:								
0	36	11.0	5.0	R	-	-	27 ^x	5.0

Remarks:

⁺Eq. (3.2.6) multiplied by $\pi/4$ for circular extended field.

^xEq. (3.2.5) multiplied by empirical correction factor 1.16.

3.3. Influence of attitude jitter on measurements

Attitude jitter can be defined as the deviation of the actual attitude (as function of time) from the a posteriori estimated attitude motion, obtained in the course of the final data processing using all available information (IDT data, star mapper data, gyros) and a detailed modelisation of known perturbing torques and the dynamics of the satellite. Sources of jitter are external torques (solar pressure, magnetic torques, etc.) to the extent they are unmodelised and not absorbed by general (e.g. polynomial) representations of the motion, gyro and reaction wheel imperfections, sloshing of liquid fuels, and structural vibrations excited e.g. by thrusters.

The sensitivity of astrometric observations to jitter is most rigorously studied by means of numerical experiments simulating the instrument, observations, and data processing. However, important insight can be gained from rather simplified considerations, as indicated below.

3.3.1. Analytical model

Only jitter around the nominal spin axis (z) deserves attention in a first approximation, thanks to the fundamental one-dimensionality of observations. The relative sensitivity to the other components of the jitter (around x and y axes) is a factor 10^{-2} lower in amplitude (cf. the discussions in Sections 2.1.5 and 3.6.2 on the a posteriori requirements on attitude knowledge). The jitter $\Delta\Psi(t)$ is a stochastic process which, at least for suitable segments of time, may be characterised by a power spectrum

$$P(f) \equiv 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R(\tau) \exp(-j2\pi f\tau) d\tau; \quad (3.3.1)$$

$$R(\tau) \equiv \langle \Delta\Psi(t) \Delta\Psi(t - \tau) \rangle \quad (3.3.2)$$

is the autocorrelation function of the process. The total jitter variance is $R(0) = \int_0^{\infty} P(f) df$.

In the first instance $\Delta\psi(t)$ influences the determination of the position of a star in the grid system. If we forget about the finer details we can say that positional information on the star (in the grid system) is gained at a constant rate as long as the IFOV stays on that star. The influence of the jitter on the observed position in the grid system is then simply the corresponding time average of $\Delta\psi(t)$. (In reality the situation is more complex: positional information is gained preferentially when the star image is at the edge of a slit; this is also when the transmitted intensity is most sensitive to jitter. This causes a certain sensitivity to jitter of frequencies near the fundamental intensity modulation frequency and its harmonics, nominally 150 Hz, 300 Hz, etc. For details, see /7/.)

The grid position of this star is eventually compared with the grid position of another star, observed in a different interval of time, and the angle between the two stars is obtained. It follows that the error on the measured angle, due to the jitter, can be written

$$\varepsilon = \int u(t) \Delta\psi(t) dt, \quad (3.3.3)$$

where $u(t) = 1/T_1$ when the IFOV is on the first star, $u(t) = -1/T_2$ when on the second star, and $u(t) = 0$ otherwise; T_i is the total time spent on star i . It is then easy to show that the variance of ε is

$$\sigma^2 = \int_0^{\infty} P(f) W(f) df, \quad (3.3.4)$$

where the window function $W(f)$ is the squared modulus of the Fourier transform of $u(t)$:

$$W(f) = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u(t) \exp(-j2\pi ft) dt \right|^2. \quad (3.3.5)$$

Fig. 3.3.1 shows an example of the function $u(t)$ for a typical scheme of interlacing observations of two stars. It is characterized by three time constants and an integer n :

- t_1 = IFOV dwell time
- t_2 = repetition interval
- t_3 = non-centrality of observations (delay)
- n = number of repetitions.

The corresponding window function is

$$\begin{aligned}
 W(f) &= W_1(f) \cdot W_2(f) \cdot W_3(f) && (3.3.6) \\
 &= \left(\frac{\sin(\pi f t_1)}{\pi f t_1} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\sin(n \pi f t_2)}{n \sin(\pi f t_2)} \right)^2 \cdot 4 \sin^2(\pi f t_3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Each of the three factors $W_1 - W_3$ has a simple interpretation. $W_1(f)$ is the suppression of high-frequency jitter ($f \gtrsim 1/t_1$) due to the averaging over the dwell time; $W_2(f)$ is the spectral transmission of the grating consisting of the n equispaced observations on each star; $W_3(f)$ finally results from taking the difference between two such sets of observations with a time difference t_3 .

Ideally, if strict simultaneity of observation was possible, we would have $t_3 = 0$, implying $W(f) = 0$, i.e. complete insensitiveness to jitter. In practice, since the IFOV can only be at one star at a time, the smallest possible delay is $t_3 = t_1$, still giving a very good suppression of low-frequency jitter.

3.3.2. Evaluation of jitter effects

With sampling frequency 1200 Hz and grid period 1" we may have, typically, $t_1 = 53$ ms (64 samples), $t_2 = 213$ ms (256 samples), $t_3 = t_1$, and $n = 8$. The resulting window function is shown in Fig. 3.3.2 (bottom). It consists mainly of a sequence of "slots" at frequencies which are positive integer multiples of $t_2^{-1} \simeq 4.7$ Hz. The bandwidth (FWHP) is always the same, $(n t_2)^{-1} \simeq 0.6$ Hz, but the height is modulated by $W_1(f) \cdot W_3(f)$. The first and second harmonics

dominate; above frequency $t_1^{-1} \approx 19$ Hz there is very little power transmitted thanks to the factor $W_1(f)$. (Note however the windows near 150 Hz and 300 Hz shown by the more detailed analysis /7/.)

The actual power spectrum of jitter is largely unknown; however, the source likely to dominate in the critical range $\sim 3 - 15$ Hz seems to be reaction wheel unbalances (if reaction wheels are envisaged), producing a narrow spectral line at the wheel frequency. The estimated jitter amplitude is 0.5 marcsec. In the worst case the wheel frequency is exactly $1/t_2$ or $2/t_2$ (4.7 resp. 9.4 Hz), in which case the jitter contribution to the variance of the angle measurement is $\sigma^2 = 1.6 (0.5/\sqrt{2})^2 = 0.20$ marcsec², or $\sigma = 0.45$ marcsec. The expected contribution, however, given that the wheel frequency falls anywhere between 0 and 20 Hz (say), is only $\sigma = 0.12$ marcsec, since the average $W(f)$ is about 0.10 over this interval.

These figures must be compared with the photon-noise induced mean error of the angle measurement, which for the same observation time on two stars of magnitude 9 is about 12 marcsec. We may conclude that reaction-wheel jitter is completely negligible in the case of well interlaced observations of pairs of stars.

If dynamical smoothing is tried the situation may be quite different. This means that we want to connect observations of brighter stars separated by more than the width of the FOV, i.e. $t_3 \gtrsim 20$ sec. Aided by Fig. 3.3.2 we can easily see what will happen to the spectral window. Only $W_3(f)$ is modified, the first maximum occurring at $f = 0.01$ Hz (for $t_3 = 50$ sec). The first slot of $W_2(f)$, near $f = 0$, is then no longer suppressed; we get effectively an average transmission $W(f) \approx 2$ in the interval $0.005 \lesssim f \lesssim 0.3$ Hz. The feasibility of dynamical smoothing depends on whether the power integrated over this interval is smaller than the photon-noise variance of the angle measurement. At present there is no obvious answer to this question. -

Figure 3.3.1. Characterisation of interlacing observations of two stars by means of the function $u(t)$.

Figure 3.3.2. Functions $W_1(f)$ and $W_2(f)$ (top), $W_3(f)$ (centre) and the resulting window function $W(f) = W_1(f) \cdot W_2(f) \cdot W_3(f)$.

3.4. Influence of photocathode inhomogeneities

The use of an image dissector (IDT) for detection of the light modulated by the grid implies that the grid and star image are imaged on the IDT photocathode. A spurious modulation of the photoelectron rate may then result from small-scale variations of photocathode sensitivity. To reduce this effect it is envisaged to introduce a slight defocussing of the star image on the photocathode, corresponding to a geometrical image size of about 5". This is about the maximum defocussing that can be tolerated if the image (further enlarged by diffraction) should be easily accommodated by the IFOV (diameter 30"), taking into account also IFOV tracking errors. The residual effects on the determination of positions in the grid system have been evaluated in reference /8/. The following is a summary of the results.

3.4.1. General result

The positional error caused by photocathode inhomogeneities is approximately given by the formula

$$b = - \frac{s}{\pi a_1 v T} \int_0^{vT} F(x) \sin(2\pi x/s) dx, \quad (3.4.1)$$

where s is the grid period, a_1 the intensity modulation factor, v the spin rate and T the observation time (IFOV dwell time). $0 \leq x \leq vT$ is the portion of the photocathode along the scan covered by the centre of the star image.

$F(x)$ is the relative deviation of photocathode sensitivity averaged over the defocussed star image with centre at (x, y) . If the defocussed image is a uniformly illuminated rectangle of length l and width w , we have

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{wl} \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} d\xi \int_{-w/2}^{w/2} \left[\frac{\sigma(x, y)}{\langle \sigma \rangle} - 1 \right] d\eta, \quad (3.4.2)$$

if $\sigma(x, y)$ is the local sensitivity and $\langle \sigma \rangle$ the global mean.

3.4.2. Numerical examples

Eqs. (3.4.1) - (3.4.2) have been evaluated with a realistic set of parameters ($s = 1''$, $a_1 = 0.5$, $v = 150''/s$, $T = 0.1$ s, $l = 5''$, $w = 2.5''$) and with various assumptions concerning $\sigma(x, y)$.

Absolute bound

It is seen from (3.4.1) that the most critical kind of sensitivity variation is a sinusoidal with period s (being $\pm \pi/2$ out of phase with the intensity modulation produced by the grid). Assuming $F(x) = B \sin(2\pi x/s)$ we find $b = -Bs/2\pi a_1$. Since the maximum amplitude of $\sigma(x, y)$ would be $\langle \sigma \rangle$, it follows from eq. (2) that $|B| \leq |\sin(\pi l/s)/(\pi l/s)| \leq s/\pi l$. Thus we obtain an absolute bound for the positional error

$$|b| \leq \frac{s^2}{2\pi^2 a_1 l} \approx 20 \text{ marcsec.} \quad (3.4.3)$$

This is however an extremely artificial worst case; with all reasonable assumptions on $\sigma(x, y)$ we should find much smaller effects.

Linear sensitivity gradient

A linear gradient $\sigma(x, y) = \sigma_0 + \sigma_1 x$ gives

$$|b| \leq (\sigma_1/\sigma_0) \frac{s^2}{2\pi^2 a_1} \approx 2.0 \text{ marcsec} \quad (3.4.4)$$

for $\sigma_1/\sigma_0 = 0.02 \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$, corresponding to 30 % variation across the distance $vT = 15''$ ($= 45 \mu\text{m}$ on the photocathode).

Blemishes

For blemishes (unsensitive spots) of all sizes we find

$$|b| \leq \frac{s^3}{\pi^3 a_1 vT l} \approx 0.9 \text{ marcsec,} \quad (3.4.5)$$

provided there is only one blemish along the image path.

Stochastic sensitivity variations

Consider the following granularity model of cathode inhomogeneities. $\sigma(x, y)$ is zero except in a finite number of randomly positioned dots, covering a percentage p of the total area. Inside each dot the sensitivity is $\langle \sigma \rangle/p$ so that the average sensitivity is preserved. Let N be the

average number of dots per unit area. The random distribution of dots will then cause an rms positional error

$$b_{\text{rms}} \approx \frac{s^2}{\pi^2 a_1 \sqrt{NwvT}} \quad (3.4.6)$$

N may be estimated as follows. If the photocathode is divided into small pixels each of area A, we expect on the average AN dots per pixel; the actual number is however subject to statistical fluctuations by $\pm \sqrt{AN}$. Since the sensitivity of a pixel will be proportional to the number of dots we should then expect random variations of relative sensitivity by $\pm 1/\sqrt{AN}$ (rms) from pixel to pixel. Now take for instance the UV converters of IUE: the quoted pixel-to-pixel variation is 5% and the pixel size is $37 \times 37 \mu\text{m}^2$, corresponding to $12 \times 12 \text{ arcsec}^2$ on the HIPPARCOS IDT photocathode. We then find $N = 2.8 \text{ arcsec}^{-2}$ and $b_{\text{rms}} = 4 \text{ marcsec}$. This is probably an upper limit since the quoted figure 5% includes also large-scale variations, which have negligible effects on the astrometric observations.

3.4.3. Conclusions

The effects of photocathode inhomogeneities computed above must always be compared with the mean error due to photon noise, which is about 20 marcsec for a 9th magnitude star and observation time $T = 0.1 \text{ sec}$. In view of this we may conclude that neither strong sensitivity gradients, blemishes of any sizes, or reasonable (although still pessimistic) random variations are likely to produce significant errors. There is consequently no need for a detailed photometric calibration of the photocathode.

3.5. Accuracy of star mapper observations

The star mapper provides calibration data for the real-time three-axes attitude determination needed for proper IDT piloting. The requirements for this purpose on accuracy and frequency of observation are modest ($\sim 1''$ for a few tens of stars distributed along the great-circle scan). A much better attitude knowledge ($\sim 0.1''$) is however required in the final data analysis (see Section 2.1). The photon statistics of star mapper observations have been examined with the view to ascertain that such an accuracy is indeed attainable for a sufficient number of stars. The results of a more extensive study /9/ are summarized below.

3.5.1. Preliminary design of star mapper

The parameters of the star mapper grid have been preliminarily optimized as follows.

Number of slits	:	8 vertical + 8 at 45°
Slit width	:	$0.6''$ in direction of scan
Distance between slit centres	:	$3.0''$ in direction of scan
Height of slit system	:	$20'$

The total area of the slits projected on the sky is $1.8 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ deg}^2$, which is sufficiently small to avoid confusion of stars (the probability of having a star brighter than 10th magnitude within a slit is $< 1\%$) and to give an acceptable background current (integrated sky brightness corresponds to one star of magnitude 11.5). A photomultiplier with a 15 mm diameter S20 photocathode is foreseen; the dark current at 20°C is 2000 Hz. Including average sky brightness the total background current is 3300 Hz.

3.5.2. Results

Table 3.5.1 gives the mean errors along the scan (σ_η) and normal to it (σ_ξ) as functions of blue star magnitude (B). The last column gives the average number (N) of programme stars per great-circle scan (2.4 h) encountered by the star mapper. It is clear that there is a sufficient number of stars and photons to allow attitude determination to at least 0.1 arcsec.

Table 3.5.1. Star mapper accuracy: mean errors along (σ_{η}) and perpendicular to the scan (σ_{ξ}) as functions of magnitude (B). M is the number of programme stars observable per scan. The mean errors given in /9/ have been multiplied by 1.5 to account for possible degradation of the MTF from the theoretical value used in /9/.

B	σ_{η}	σ_{ξ}	M
7	0".012	0".022	70
8	0.023	0.042	130
9	0.045	0.084	160
10	0.10	0.18	90
11	0.24	0.42	50
12	0.57	1.1	10

3.6. Scientific data processing

The purpose and extent of the scientific data processing are defined by the input and output data specifications. Input data are:

- a catalogue of observed objects with identification, categorisation, and a priori astrometric and photometric data;
- the IDT count record, i.e. the sequence of photoelectron counts (or equivalent) for the entire mission;
- the star mapper count record, containing the photomultiplier counts (or equivalent), possibly in a compressed form;
- the gyro readings;
- the observation log, containing timing of samples and object identifications for IDT and star mapper observations;
- calibration data obtained in the laboratory and in orbit;
- the heliocentric satellite ephemerides $[\underline{r}(t), \underline{\dot{r}}(t)]$.

The output consists of the catalogue with updated (a posteriori) astrometric and photometric data on the observed objects. In particular, the positions and proper motions are given in a consistent, but not necessarily absolute or inertial, celestial reference system. Trigonometric parallaxes are quasi-absolute, i.e. a global zero-point error may be present. Detectable double stars are characterised by additional parameters. The output catalogue should also provide information on the quality of data, e.g. estimated mean errors, number of observations, and rms residuals.

It is obvious that the scientific processing is a big and complex task which may be carried out in many different ways and even according to entirely different philosophies, particularly concerning basic estimation methods (e.g. Bayesian versus least-squares approach) and the degree of modelisation of instrument and attitude motion. It is in fact desirable

that the entire processing is undertaken by at least two institutes or groups of institutes, working, as far as practicable, independently and along different lines.

The processing scheme outlined in the following aims at taking into account all the factors which are believed to be crucial for obtaining the stated accuracy, with a minimum of refinement; it is recognised that there are other schemes which may be simpler, cheaper, more rigorous, or more elegant. The basic observation model given here and the reconstitution of the sphere are a synthesis of earlier concepts /5, 11/ and new inputs mainly from K. Poder at the Danish Geodetic Institute (cf. /26 - 27/).

3.6.1. Description of main input/output data

The catalogue (I/O) contains astrometric and photometric data on each star ($i = 1, 2, \dots, \sim 10^5$). The astrometric parameters of star no. i are mainly the following five:

- $\bar{\beta}_i$ = ecliptical latitude at epoch T;
- $\bar{\lambda}_i$ = ecliptical longitude at epoch T;
- $\mu_{\beta i}$ = yearly proper motion in latitude;
- $\mu_{\lambda i}$ = yearly proper motion in longitude;
- w_i = trigonometric parallax.

Ecliptical coordinates refer to a fixed ecliptic and equinox as defined by a fundamental star catalogue (FK5) and adopted astronomical constants. In practice it will be preferred to work in equatorial coordinates (referred to fixed equator and equinox), but the difference is of no importance for the present discussion, since transformation between the two systems is trivial.

For resolved double and multiple stars additional parameters are needed. Usually, the relative motion of the components of a double star is negligible. Only two extra astrometric parameters are then needed, e.g. separation ρ_i and position angle of secondary Θ_i .

The photometric parameters are the apparent magnitude m_i in the instrument system ($\sim$ Johnson B) and a colour index c_i ; for double stars the magnitude and colour differences $\Delta m_i, \Delta c_i$

are added. Estimates of m_i and Δm_i are obtained in the data processing, but the colours are used only as inputs (when available).

The IDT count record consists of the photoelectron counts (samples) N_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, \sim 10^{11}$. The time t_k of each sample is known from the observation log and also which star was observed i_k . A subset of $\{N_k\}$ belonging to the same star i and obtained within a short time interval $\delta t \sim 2$ sec may be called an elementary observation. It is referred to the mid-time of the observation interval:

$$\mathcal{N}(i, t) \equiv \left\{ N_k : i_k = i \text{ and } t - \frac{1}{2}\delta t \leq t_k \leq t + \frac{1}{2}\delta t \right\}. \quad (3.6.1)$$

It is assumed that the rapid switching of the IFOV between different stars allows the elementary observations of two or more stars to be referred to the same instant t (effectively simultaneous observations).

The star mapper count record $\{N'_k\}$ contains photoelectron counts sampled synchronously with the IDT data ($t'_k = t_k$). However, since there is no programme star near the star mapper slits most of the time, only a small fraction of the samples ($\sim 2\%$) is down-linked. The observation log provides the star identifications i'_k . In analogy with (3.6.1) we may define the elementary star mapper observation as the set of counts $\mathcal{N}'_u(i, t')$ of the passage of star i across the eight vertical ($u = 0$) or inclined slits ($u = \pm 45^\circ$). t' is the approximate time of passage.

The gyro data consists of readings of the three (or four) gyros, each sensing the angular velocity (or rather the incremental attitude) around a particular axis. The sampling rate is of the order of 5 - 50 Hz, preferably a suitable integer fraction of the IDT and star mapper sampling rate.

3.6.2. Basic observation model

The scientific data processing relies on a mathematical model relating the observed quantities (IDT and star mapper data and gyro readings) to the required astrometric parameters.

Thanks to the regularity and one-dimensionality of the main grid and the limited support of the MTF, the modulated intensity falling on the IDT is a periodic function of the position of the image along the grid, and contains only a small number of harmonics. Only the first two harmonics are of importance; the photoelectron counts are thus modelised as a realisation of the Poisson process with intensity

$$I_k = a_0 + a_1 [M_1 \cos(2\pi G_k + v_1) + M_2 \cos(4\pi G_k + v_2)] \quad (3.6.2)$$

G_k is the grid coordinate of the image at time t_k , i.e. number of slits counted from FOV edge or similar. M_1 , M_2 , v_1 and v_2 are quantities known from the laboratory calibrations of the grid and the instrument OTF. They are in general functions of star colour and the field coordinates (η , ζ , and f ; η and ζ are angles from the field centre along and normal to the scan; f is ± 1 for preceding and following field, respectively). $v_1(\eta, \zeta, f)$ and $v_2(\eta, \zeta, f)$ include in particular the calibrated small-scale distortions of the grid and optical fields. a_0 and a_1 are photometric parameters related to the intensities of the background and star, respectively. We shall express G_k in terms of the astrometric parameters, attitude parameters, and instrumental parameters.

At the time of the elementary observation $\mathcal{N}(i, t)$ the apparent celestial coordinates of the star are well-defined functions of the astrometric parameters and the heliocentric radius vector and velocity vector of the satellite [$\underline{r}(t)$ and $\dot{\underline{r}}(t)$]:

$$\beta_i(t) \equiv \beta[\bar{\beta}_i, \bar{\lambda}_i, \mu_{\beta i}, \mu_{\lambda i}, \varpi_i, \underline{r}(t), \dot{\underline{r}}(t), t] \quad (3.6.3)$$

$$\lambda_i(t) \equiv \lambda[\bar{\beta}_i, \bar{\lambda}_i, \mu_{\beta i}, \mu_{\lambda i}, \varpi_i, \underline{r}(t), \dot{\underline{r}}(t), t].$$

$\underline{r}(t)$ and $\dot{\underline{r}}(t)$, which are needed for computing the parallax factor and the aberration and relativistic deflection of the light, are accurately known from independent observations. $\underline{r}(t)$ gives the satellitocentric ecliptical coordinates of the sun through

$$\underline{r}(t) = (-r \cos \beta_0 \cos \lambda_0, -r \cos \beta_0 \sin \lambda_0, -r \sin \beta_0). \quad (3.6.4)$$

The differentials of (3.6.3) are, to first order,

$$\begin{aligned} d\beta_i &= d\bar{\beta}_i + (t-T)d\mu_{\beta_i} - r(t) \sin \bar{\beta}_i \cos [\bar{\lambda}_i - \lambda_0(t)] d\omega_i \\ d\lambda_i &= d\bar{\lambda}_i + (t-T)d\mu_{\lambda_i} - r(t) \frac{1}{\cos \bar{\beta}_i} \sin [\bar{\lambda}_i - \lambda_0(t)] d\omega_i. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.5)$$

We introduce now the nominal telescope frame (x,y,z) defined by the two unit vectors $\hat{n}_f, \hat{n}_p$ normal to the two faces of the complex mirror:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{x} &= (\hat{n}_f + \hat{n}_p) / |\hat{n}_f + \hat{n}_p| \\ \hat{y} &= \hat{z} \wedge \hat{x} \\ \hat{z} &= (\hat{n}_f \wedge \hat{n}_p) / |\hat{n}_f \wedge \hat{n}_p|. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.6)$$

The plane containing $\hat{n}_f$ and $\hat{n}_p$ is the principal plane; its intersection with the celestial sphere is the principal great circle (PGC). The basic angle Υ is twice the acute angle between $\hat{n}_f$ and $\hat{n}_p$.

The attitude of the telescope is defined by the three angles $\beta_z(t), \lambda_z(t), \omega(t)$. The first two give the instantaneous ecliptical coordinates of $\hat{z}$; the third is the anomaly of $\hat{x}$, i.e. the angle along PGC from the ecliptic (ascending node) to $\hat{x}$ (Fig. 3.6.1).

The field coordinates $\eta_i(t), \zeta_i(t), f_i(t)$ of star i at time t are then defined by the equations (dropping index and time argument for brevity)

$$\begin{aligned} f &= \text{sign}(y) \\ x &= \cos \zeta \cos(\eta + \frac{1}{2}f\Upsilon) \\ y &= \cos \zeta \sin(\eta + \frac{1}{2}f\Upsilon) \\ z &= \sin \zeta. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.7)$$

Figure 3.6.1. Definition of angles for the instantaneous telescope attitude. Designations:

- EE', N = ecliptic and pole
- S = star, (β , λ)
- Z, X = axes of the nominal telescope frame
- PGC = principal great circle
- Ω = PGC ascending node
- F, P = directions of optical axes
- ζ , η = field coordinates
- ω = ΩX = anomaly of scan

From the spherical triangle NSZ we find (Fig. 3.6.1)

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \frac{\pi}{2} - \omega - q_z - \frac{1}{2}f\gamma \\ \sin \zeta &= \sin \beta_z \sin \beta_i + \cos \beta_z \cos \beta_i \cos(\lambda_i - \lambda_z) \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.8)$$

where q_z is obtained from

$$\begin{aligned} \sin q_z &= \cos \beta_i \sin(\lambda_i - \lambda_z) / \cos \zeta \\ \cos q_z &= (\sin \beta_i - \sin \beta_z \sin \zeta) / \cos \beta_z \cos \zeta \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.9)$$

The angle at S is given by the analogous formulae

$$\begin{aligned} \sin q &= \cos \beta_z \sin(\lambda_i - \lambda_z) / \cos \zeta \\ \cos q &= (\sin \beta_z - \sin \beta_i \sin \zeta) / \cos \beta_i \cos \zeta \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.10)$$

Differentiation of (3.6.7) yields

$$\begin{aligned} d\eta &= \frac{\sin q}{\cos \zeta} d\beta_i + \frac{\cos q}{\cos \zeta} d\lambda_i \cos \beta_i - \tan \zeta \sin q_z d\beta_z + \\ &+ \tan \zeta \cos q_z d\lambda_z \cos \beta_z - \frac{1}{2}f d\gamma - (d\omega + d\lambda_z \sin \beta_z) \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} d\zeta &= \cos q d\beta_i - \sin q d\lambda_i \cos \beta_i + \\ &+ \cos q_z d\beta_z + \sin q_z d\lambda_z \cos \beta_z. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.12)$$

Note that the attitude differentials $d\beta_z$ and $d\lambda_z \cos \beta_z$ enter into (3.6.11) multiplied by a small factor $|\tan \zeta| \lesssim 0.008$, except by the term $d\omega + d\lambda_z \sin \beta_z$, which is in fact the rotation component around $\hat{z}$ ($d\psi$). This is fundamental to the present one-dimensional measurement principle: the attitude components around $\hat{x}$ and $\hat{y}$ enter as second-order terms and are needed only to ~ 0.1 arcsec, and errors of the third attitude component are eliminated by making differential, quasi-simultaneous observations.

Recalling that the small-scale grid and field distortions are largely eliminated by means of the calibrations $v_1(\eta, \zeta, f)$ and $v_2(\eta, \zeta, f)$, we may adopt a polynomial transformation of field coordinates to grid coordinates:

$$G(\eta, \zeta, f) = \sum_{m=0}^{\cdot} \sum_{n=0}^{\cdot} (g_{mn} + fh_{mn}) \eta^m \zeta^n. \quad (3.6.13)$$

This takes care of in particular the displacement and rotation of the grid and the low-order optical distortions, which are the only ones which may conceivably change during the lifetime of the satellite. Differentiation yields

$$dG = \sum_m \sum_n (dg_{mn} + f dh_{mn}) \eta^m \zeta^n + (g_{10} + g_{11}\zeta + 2g_{20}\eta) d\eta + g_{01} d\zeta. \quad (3.6.14)$$

For the short duration of the elementary observation, the relative attitude motion in η and ζ are given, to sufficient accuracy, by the gyros; hence we may assume that

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\eta_k &\equiv \eta(t_k) - \eta(t) \\ \Delta\zeta_k &\equiv \zeta(t_k) - \zeta(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.15)$$

are known prior to the processing of the IDT data. If $\bar{G}(i, t)$ is the mean grid coordinate of the elementary observation $\mathcal{N}(i, t)$ we have then

$$G_k = \bar{G}(i, t) + (g_{10} + g_{11}\zeta + 2g_{20}\eta)\Delta\eta_k + g_{01}\Delta\zeta_k. \quad (3.6.16)$$

The complete observation model for $\mathcal{N}(i, t)$ thus involves the following parameters:

- the astrometric parameters $\bar{\beta}_i, \bar{\lambda}_i, \mu_{\beta i}, \mu_{\lambda i}, \varpi_i$;
- the telescope attitude parameters $\beta_z(t), \lambda_z(t), \omega(t)$;
- the instrument parameters $\gamma(t), g_{mn}(t), h_{mn}(t)$;
- the local photometric parameters $a_0(i, t), a_1(i, t)$.

It is also necessary to modelise the time dependent attitude and instrument parameters (discretisation and possible continuity conditions); from the point of view of data processing the simplest model is the following, which may be fully adequate and is adopted in the sequel.

- $\beta_z(t)$, $\lambda_z(t)$, and provisional $\omega(t)$ are obtained almost continuously by integration of the gyro readings; the necessary modelisation is thus incorporated in the attitude reconstitution algorithm (smoother).
- The precise anomaly $\omega(t)$ is obtained independently for each group of elementary observations referred to same t . This is of course the most conservative approach (no dynamical smoothing).
- $\gamma(t)$, $g_{mn}(t)$, and $h_{mn}(t)$ are assumed to be constant over a set of consecutive scans (~ 12 hours) and determined independently for each set.

This completes the modelisation of the IDT data.

The star mapper observation $\mathcal{N}'_u(i, t')$ is similarly modelised; the previous formulae apply with minor modifications due to the different slit configurations and the lower precision aimed at. Because of the larger grid period, more terms are needed in the Fourier series representation (3.6.2). The calibration parameters M'_{ju} , v'_{ju} depend of course also on the inclination of the slits (u), and the same goes for the transformation coefficients g'_{mnu} , h'_{mnu} , which can be regarded as known from laboratory measurements.

3.6.3. Data processing scheme

Fig. 3.6.2 outlines the general organization of the scientific data processing. Rectangular boxes indicate data files, which may be updated if included in a loop; the oval boxes indicate procedures operating on the data. The processing is roughly divided in four strongly interdependent tasks:

- a posteriori attitude reconstitution (upper left quadrant of Fig. 3.6.2);
- determination of grid coordinates $\bar{G}(i,t)$ for elementary IDT observations (upper right quadrant);
- reconstitution of the celestial sphere (Step 1-3, lower left quadrant);
- double-star detection (lower right quadrant).

Parts of these tasks must be performed twice or several times, as they partake in a bigger iteration loop.

3.6.3.1. A posteriori attitude reconstitution

Inputs to this task are gyro readings, star mapper observations, and (a priori or updated) catalogue positions of the stars. Raw star mapper data are pre-processed to a format suitable for the reconstitution proper.

Pre-processing of star mapper data. The pre-processing extracts from each elementary observation $\mathcal{N}'_u(i,t')$ the relevant signal parameters, i.e. in particular the estimated time of transit at the (say) middle slit; and the variance of the estimate. This may involve the following steps:

- in-flight calibration of modulation parameters M'_{ju}, v'_{ju} , e.g. by Fourier analysis of the first few days of observation. In effect, this yields the average normalised light curve $I'_u(t)$;
- checking the catalogue for possible duplicity or other parasitic stars. Observations suspected to be significantly disturbed are rejected;

Figure 3.6.2. Organization of scientific data processing.

- fitting the average normalised light curve to observed counts e.g. by the model

$$N'_k = a'_0 + a'_1 I'_u(t_k - a'_2) + \text{noise}, \quad (3.6.17)$$

and computing a goodness-of-fit measure (χ^2);

- establish and apply acceptance criteria based on χ^2 and estimated variances.

After a period of exploratory processing and calibration at the beginning of the mission, the pre-processing is carried out with short delay and little monitoring, e.g. in batches once per day, and relevant signal parameters stored for subsequent processing.

Attitude reconstitution. Compared with the real-time attitude determination on board the satellite, the a posteriori processing takes advantage of the larger number of star mapper observations, a more careful pre-processing of them, much more accurate star positions from the (eventually) updated catalogue, and the use of a smoothing algorithm instead of a predictor. A linear fixed-lag smoother with a time lag of at least a few minutes can be employed; since this is a classical problem and the implementation rather uncritical we do not detail it here.

3.6.3.2. Determination of grid coordinates

IDT data pre-processing. The down-linked samples $\{N_k\}$ comprise $\sim 10^{12}$ bits, corresponding to ~ 5000 magnetic tapes. Even if the complete set of raw data is saved for some time after the completion of the mission, it is necessary to extract the essential information (signal parameters) shortly after observation and store them compactly, yet in a form suitable for subsequent use. The preprocessing takes advantage of the limited harmonic content of the signal and the preliminary a posteriori attitude (based on inaccurate star positions) available within a day or so of the observation. Thus, the relative grid phase

$$H_k \equiv 2\pi \left[(\varepsilon_{10} + \varepsilon_{11} \zeta + 2\varepsilon_{20} \eta) \Delta \eta_k + \varepsilon_{01} \Delta \zeta_k \right] \quad (3.6.18)$$

is known for each elementary observation. Assuming that the signal contains only the first and second harmonics, we have the perfectly general intensity model

$$I_k(\underline{b}) \equiv b_1 + b_2 \cos(H_k + b_3) + b_4 \cos(2H_k + 2b_3) + b_5 \sin(2H_k + 2b_3), \quad (3.6.19)$$

depending only on the five-dimensional parameter vector $\underline{b} = (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5)^t$. Note that (3.6.19) is valid for single and multiple stars alike; eq. (3.6.2) is only a special case of it.

It is well known that, given the parametrised model $I_k(\underline{b})$, a sufficient description of the observation $\mathcal{N}(i, t)$ is provided by the (relative logarithmic) likelihood function

$$l(\underline{b}) \equiv \sum_k \left[N_k \ln I_k(\underline{b}) - I_k(\underline{b}) \right]. \quad (3.6.20)$$

Unfortunately, this expression cannot be further simplified; the set of actual counts $\mathcal{N}(i, t)$ is in fact the simplest exact representation of $l(\underline{b})$. However, we are in practice concerned only with a small region of the parameter space near the true parameter vector, in which $l(\underline{b})$ may be expanded in a Taylor series. Let $\hat{\underline{b}}$ be the maximum likelihood estimate of $\underline{b}$,

$$\left. \frac{\partial l(\underline{b})}{\partial b_j} \right|_{\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}}} = 0, \quad 1 \leq j \leq 5. \quad (3.6.21)$$

Expanding up to the second order around $\hat{\underline{b}}$ we find

$$l(\underline{b}) = l(\hat{\underline{b}}) - \frac{1}{2} (\underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}})^t \underline{F} (\underline{b} - \hat{\underline{b}}), \quad (3.6.22)$$

where the elements of the Fisher matrix $\underline{F}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} F_{ij} &= -E \left[\frac{\partial^2 l(\underline{b})}{\partial b_i \partial b_j} \Big|_{\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}}} \right] \\ &= \sum_k \frac{1}{I_k(\hat{\underline{b}})} \frac{\partial I_k}{\partial b_i} \frac{\partial I_k}{\partial b_j}, \quad 1 \leq i, j \leq 5. \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.23)$$

Practically all information contained in the elementary observation is thus conveyed by the 20 signal parameters $\hat{\underline{b}}$ and $\underline{F}$ (the latter being symmetric). The reduction of storage compared with the original 500 - 1000 samples is a factor 5 - 10 (counting four samples per real number). In practice, it is convenient to store the covariance matrix $\underline{F}^{-1}$ rather than $\underline{F}$.

Determination of grid coordinates (location estimator).

For a single star the intensity is given by (3.6.2) and (3.6.16) in terms of the three parameters a_0 , a_1 , and $\bar{G}(i,t)$. These are related to the five parameters $\underline{b}$ in (3.6.19) by

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= a_0 \\ b_2 &= a_1 M_1 \\ b_3 &= 2\pi\bar{G}(i,t) + v_1 \\ b_4 &= a_1 M_2 \cos(2v_1 - v_2) \\ b_5 &= a_1 M_2 \sin(2v_1 - v_2). \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.24)$$

If M_1 , M_2 , v_1 , v_2 are regarded as known, (3.6.2) is in fact a sub-model of (3.6.19) constrained by two linear equations:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{M_2}{M_1} b_2 + \cos(2v_1 - v_2) b_4 + \sin(2v_1 - v_2) b_5 &= 0, \\ \sin(2v_1 - v_2) b_4 - \cos(2v_1 - v_2) b_5 &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.25)$$

or, in matrix form $\underline{c}\underline{b} = 0$, where $\underline{c}$ is a known 2x5 matrix. Maximum likelihood estimation of $\bar{G}(i,k)$ thus amounts to maximising the Lagrangean function

$$L(\underline{b}, \underline{\lambda}) = l(\underline{b}) - \underline{\lambda}^t \underline{c} \underline{b}, \quad (3.6.26)$$

where $\underline{\lambda}^t = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$ is a vector of Lagrangean multipliers. With the approximation (3.6.22) the conditions $\partial L / \partial b_j = 0$, $\partial L / \partial \lambda_m = 0$ becomes a system of seven linear equations:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \underline{F} & \underline{c}^t \\ \underline{c} & \underline{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \underline{b} \\ \underline{\lambda} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \underline{F}\hat{\underline{b}} \\ \underline{0} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.6.27)$$

The solution is

$$\underline{b} = \hat{\underline{b}} - \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{c}^t (\underline{c} \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{c}^t)^{-1} \underline{c} \hat{\underline{b}}, \quad (3.6.28)$$

and the logarithm of the likelihood ratio with respect to the unconstrained fit $\hat{\underline{b}}$ is

$$l(\underline{b}) - l(\hat{\underline{b}}) = -\frac{1}{2} \hat{\underline{b}}^t \underline{c}^t (\underline{c} \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{c}^t)^{-1} \underline{c} \hat{\underline{b}}. \quad (3.6.29)$$

Thus, the computation of the constrained estimate of $\bar{G}(i,t)$ from $\hat{\underline{b}}$ and $\underline{F}^{-1}$ involves only simple non-iterative operations, including inversion of the 2x2 matrix $(\underline{c} \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{c}^t)$.

For a double star the unconstrained solution $\hat{\underline{b}}$ provides the additional information on the projected separation of the stars and their relative intensity; however, the combination of many elementary observations of the same double star for obtaining its astrometric parameters depends on many trial solutions with different constraints (see Section 3.6.3.4). The likelihood ratio (3.6.29) is important for double-star detection.

3.6.3.3. Reconstitution of the celestial sphere

Given the approximate attitude, the grid coordinates $\bar{G}(i,t)$, the preliminary catalogue and calibration data, the updated astrometric and instrument parameters are obtained by a (possibly iterated) three-step procedure.

Step 1: solution of sets. The elementary observations on a number of (say five) consecutive scans are called a set. Each set contains ~70 000 elementary observations on ~1800 stars. The complete mission comprises ~2000 sets.

For each set we introduce a reference great circle (RGC) by selecting its exact pole (β_r, λ_r) near the average position of $\hat{\underline{z}}$ for the set. In analogy with (3.6.8) - (3.6.10) we define the angles q_r , Q , and ζ_r of a star with respect to the RGC (Fig. 3.6.3):

$$\sin \zeta_r = \sin \beta_i \sin \beta_r + \cos \beta_i \cos \beta_r \cos(\lambda_i - \lambda_r) \quad (3.6.30)$$

$$\sin q_r = \cos \beta_i \sin(\lambda_i - \lambda_r) / \cos \zeta_r \quad (3.6.31)$$

$$\cos q_r = (\sin \beta_i - \sin \beta_r \sin \zeta_r) / \cos \beta_r \cos \zeta_r$$

Figure 3.6.3. Definition of ordinate and abscissa.

Designations:

- EE', N = ecliptic and pole
- S = star, (β, λ)
- R = pole of RGC, (β_r, λ_r)
- RGC = reference great circle
- α = abscissa of S
- ξ_r = ordinate of S

$$\begin{aligned}\sin Q &= \cos \beta_r \sin(\lambda_i - \lambda_r) / \cos \zeta_r \\ \cos Q &= (\sin \beta_r - \sin \beta_i \sin \zeta_r) / \cos \beta_i \cos \zeta_r\end{aligned}\quad (3.6.32)$$

In fact, the RGC defines a temporary celestial coordinate system where (β_i, λ_i) are replaced by (ζ_{ri}, α_i) , where ζ_{ri} and $\alpha_i = \frac{1}{2}\pi - q_{ri}$ are called the ordinate and abscissa of the star. The transformation between the two systems is uniquely defined by (β_r, λ_r) and exactly known. The differentials of the transformation are

$$\begin{aligned}d\beta_i &= \sin Q \cos \zeta_{ri} d\alpha_i + \cos Q d\zeta_{ri} \\ d\lambda_i \cos \beta_i &= \cos Q \cos \zeta_{ri} d\alpha_i - \sin Q d\zeta_{ri}\end{aligned}\quad (3.6.33)$$

Insertion into (3.6.11) and (3.6.12) yields

$$\begin{aligned}d\eta &= \frac{\cos \zeta_{ri}}{\cos \zeta} \cos(q - Q) d\alpha_i + \frac{1}{\cos \zeta} \sin(q - Q) d\zeta_{ri} - \tan \zeta \sin q_z d\beta_z \\ &+ \tan \zeta \cos q_z d\lambda_z \cos \beta_z - \frac{1}{2} f d\gamma - (dw + d\lambda_z \sin \beta_z),\end{aligned}\quad (3.6.34)$$

$$\begin{aligned}d\zeta &= -\sin(q - Q) \cos \zeta_{ri} d\alpha_i + \cos(q - Q) d\zeta_{ri} + \\ &+ \cos q_z d\beta_z + \sin q_z d\lambda_z \cos \beta_z.\end{aligned}\quad (3.6.35)$$

The angle $q - Q$ (RSZ in Fig. 3.6.3) is small if $\hat{z}$ is close to the pole of the RGC. Typically $|q - Q| < 1.5^\circ$ in a set, so that the coefficient of $d\zeta_{ri}$ in (3.6.34) is numerically less than 0.03, while the coefficient of $d\alpha_i$ is ~ 1 . Thus, if ζ_{ri} is known to $\sim 0''.03$ or better, and β_z and $\lambda_z \cos \beta_z$ to $\sim 0''.1$, the corresponding terms in (3.6.35) can be neglected. Inserting into (3.6.24) and noting that $\epsilon_{01}/\epsilon_{10}$ is a small number (grid rotation), we obtain the observation equation for the grid coordinate

$$\begin{aligned}d\bar{G}(i, t) &= (\epsilon_{10} + \epsilon_{11}\zeta + 2\epsilon_{20}\eta) \frac{\cos \zeta_{ri} \cos(q - Q)}{\cos \zeta} d\alpha_i + \\ &+ \sum_m \sum_n (d\epsilon_{mn} + f dh_{mn}) \eta^m \zeta^n - dw'(t),\end{aligned}\quad (3.6.36)$$

where $d\omega' = d\omega + d\lambda_z \sin \beta_z$ and $d\lambda$ is absorbed by dh_{00} . dg_{00} may be absorbed by $d\omega'$.

The observation equations (3.6.36) for a set involves ~ 1800 abscissas ($d\alpha_i$), $\sim 17\,000$ arguments ($d\omega'$), and a dozen or so instrument parameters (dg_{mn} , dh_{mn}). The arguments can be eliminated successively while forming the normal equations; the resulting system of equations is of order ~ 1800 and rather sparse ($\sim 4\%$ filled). The abscissa origin is arbitrarily fixed e.g. by adding, formally, the a priori abscissa observation equations $d\alpha_i = 0$, given sufficiently low weight.

The abscissa solutions are accumulated on a file where results are stored according to star identification number.

Step 2: solution of Primary Stars network. The abscissas obtained in the set solutions are relative in the sense that all abscissas in a particular set may have a common zero-point error (dA_s for set s). The true abscissas defined by (3.6.30) - (3.6.31) ($\alpha_i = \frac{1}{2}\pi - q_{ri}$) are obtained by adding dA_s to the abscissa solutions. The ~ 2000 set zero-points are determined indirectly by means of a subset of the observed stars, the Primary System (PRS), containing some 500 - 1000 relatively bright single (or unresolved double) stars and forming a reasonably homogeneous network over the whole sky.

The observation equation for a PRS abscissa observation is obtained by solving $d\alpha_i$ from (3.6.33), inserting the astrometric parameters differentials (3.6.5), and adding the set zero-point:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d\alpha_i \cos \zeta_{ri} &= \sin Q d\bar{\beta}_i + \cos Q d\bar{\lambda}_i \cos \bar{\beta}_i + \\
 &+ (t - T) \sin Q d\mu_{\beta i} + (t - T) \cos Q d\mu_{\lambda i} \cos \bar{\beta}_i - \\
 &- r \left[\sin Q \sin \bar{\beta}_i \cos(\bar{\lambda}_i - \lambda_{\odot}) + \cos Q \sin(\bar{\lambda}_i - \lambda_{\odot}) \right] d\varpi_i - \\
 &- \cos \zeta_{ri} dA_s. \qquad (3.6.37)
 \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding normal equations are successively accumulated as the set solutions proceed (there are on the average 10 - 20 PRS stars per set), and dA_s are at the same time eliminated

(like dw' in Step 1). When all sets have been processed, the PRS normal equations are complete and ready to be solved. The system has 2500 - 5000 unknowns (the astrometric parameters of the PRS stars) and is fairly dense. Because of the six degrees of freedom of any non-inertial system of positions and proper motions, the PRS normal equations do not have full rank. The singularity is removed by adding the FK5 positions and proper motions of the PRS stars as low-weight observations. This ensures at the same time that the final catalogue will be, on the average, on the FK5 system. (For a discussion of the rigidity concept in relation to the spherical reconstitution problem, see /22/.)

Step 3: back-substitution and solution of individual stars.

Back-substitution of PRS astrometric parameters into (3.6.37) yields the abscissa zero-points dA_s . Then, for each individual star, the abscissa solutions are corrected by dA_s and the observation equations for the astrometric parameters formed (in fact (3.6.37) without the last term) and solved for the five unknowns. For a single star this completes the catalogue updating.

3.6.4. Double-star detection

Resolved double stars ($\rho_i \lesssim 0''.2$, $m_i \gtrsim 3$) may be detected (if not already known) by means of the increased likelihood ratios (3.6.29) due to intensity model mismatch and increased residuals in the Step 3 solution. The two effects can be combined in a total likelihood ratio with natural logarithm

$$R = \sum_s (\Delta l_s - \frac{1}{2} r_s^2 / \sigma_s^2), \quad (3.6.38)$$

where Δl_s is the sum of (3.6.29) for the elementary observations of a particular star in a set (s), and r_s and σ_s are the residual of the abscissa of the star and its standard deviation in the set. If R exceeds a certain value, the single-star hypothesis is rejected and a search begins for the main double-star parameters ρ_i , Θ_i , and Δm_i .

Unfortunately there seems to be no direct way of solving the double-star parameters. Given some trial values of ρ_i , Θ_i , and Δm_i , modified signal-parameter constraints $\underline{c}$ are easily derived and hence modified grid coordinates and $l(\underline{b}) - l(\hat{\underline{b}})$; then modified abscissas may be estimated and, using the Step 3 observation equations, modified astrometric parameters and residuals. Finally, a modified R may be computed. By such systematic mapping of $R(\rho_i, \Theta_i, \Delta m_i)$ the global maximum may eventually be found and thus the astrometric parameters of the double star. What prevents a direct solution is the complex structure of $R(\rho_i, \Theta_i, \Delta m_i)$. In terms of the relative coordinates of the components $\rho_i \cos \Theta_i$, $\rho_i \sin \Theta_i$, the function R have local maxima typically separated by the grid period (cf. Fig. 4 in /10/); so, if the entire IFOV ($\sim 30''$ diameter) must be searched for the companion star, this means that R must be computed at several thousand points. For most double stars we have fortunately sufficient a priori information to restrict the search to a small region. However, an efficient method for dealing with double stars remains to be developed.

The double-star detection algorithm will also be able to detect and correct the not unfrequent cases when the grid coordinate $\bar{G}(i,t)$ is wrong by ± 1 because of inaccurate a priori star positions.

3.7. OTF computations: Effects of misalignment

and deformation of optical elements

The software package developed by AML for the theoretical study of accuracy includes a set of programmes for rigorous computation of the optical transfer function (OTF) of the Baker-Schmidt telescope /11 - 14/. The modulus (MTF) and argument (phase, PTF) of the OTF are computed as functions of spatial frequency along a given direction and for any wavelength and object direction (field coordinates η, ζ).^{*} It includes options for the study of

- various entrance pupil shapes (circular or rectangular, symmetric or asymmetric);
- all kinds of misalignments, i.e. displacements and rotations, of each optical element (complex mirror, primary mirror, secondary mirror) and, for the symmetrical pupil, lack of parallelism of the two outer surfaces of the complex mirror;
- arbitrary deformations of all optical surfaces, represented by bidimensional splines or Fourier expansions.

In addition, the apparent displacement of a star image may be calculated as function of spatial frequency by integration with respect to wavelength, taking into account the spectral sensitivity curve of the instrument and the spectral type of the star. This allows evaluation of residual chromatic effects.

The performance of the nominal instrument and its sensitivity to perturbations have been studied by means of extensive runs of these programmes on the ICL 4/72 computer at ESOC. The following is a summary of results from previously reported experiments /23 - 25/ and subsequent undocumented runs (Vaghi, June - July, 1979).

^{*}The relation between OTF, MTF, and PTF is: $OTF = MTF \exp(i PTF)$. MTF is normalized to unity at zero spatial frequency. PTF is referred to the geometrical image point defined by the principal ray.

3.7.1. Nominal telescope

The nominal characteristics of the telescope are summarized in Table 3.7.1.

A study of the circular symmetric entrance pupil (complex mirror with three faces, the external faces nominally in one plane) showed that a lack of parallelism of 1" between the external faces, already representing a very good manufacturing performance, would result in a catastrophic degradation of the transfer function /23/. For this reason the asymmetric pupil (two-faces complex mirror) was adopted as baseline. Moreover, the rectangular pupil was preferred to the circular because of the improved MTF at intermediate spatial frequencies and the more linear PTF (giving smaller chromatic errors) /12/. Thus, all computations discussed below concern the rectangular asymmetric pupil.

Table 3.7.1. Nominal characteristics of the telescope

Curvature radius of primary mirror :	2.044	m
Curvature radius of secondary mirror :	1.102	m
Distance primary - secondary :	0.700	m
Distance primary - complex mirror (pupil) :	1.300	m
Distance primary - focal surface :	- 0.07473	m
Equivalent focal length :	2.459	m
Field curvature radius :	1.196	m
Deformation coefficient of primary :	0.4776	
Deformation coefficient of secondary :	1.2122	
Deformation coefficient of complex mirror :	- 0.01511	m ⁻³
Inclination of complex mirror surfaces ($\alpha/4$) :	± 18.0	deg
Rectangular asymmetric pupil : -		
Length :	0.25	m
Width (per field) :	0.0982	m
Linear obscuration ratio :	0.44	
Collecting aperture (per field) :	0.0198	m ²

Table 3.7.6. Degradation of MTF and chromaticity (in 10^{-3} arcsec) due to periodic deformations [eq. (3.7.3)] of complex mirror and secondary mirror (field 1; fundamental frequency of the grid). Percentage change of MTF and chromaticity change are relative to the values for the nominal telescope, Table 3.7.2.

	Degradation of MTF			Relative chromaticity		
	-20'6	0	20'6	-20'6	0	20'6
Deformed complex mirror :						
20'6	-2.8%	-3.2%	-3.8%	+2.8	+3.4	+3.6
0	-1.3	-1.8	-2.1	+2.9	+3.0	+2.9
-20'6	+0.2	-0.0	-0.8	+3.2	+2.8	+2.3
Deformed secondary mirror :						
20'6	-1.9	-3.8	-4.9	-1.3	+3.7	+2.6
0	-2.0	-2.2	-3.2	-0.8	+3.3	+3.2
-20'6	-3.1	-0.2	-1.3	+0.1	+3.0	+3.7

Table 3.7.2 gives results of the OTF computations for the nominal telescope (intersection angle $\alpha = 0$, i.e. along η). The top part of the table shows the normalized MTF and the middle part the displacement (in 10^{-3} arcsec) of an F-type star,

$$\Delta\eta(F) = \frac{ns}{2\pi} \text{PTF}, \quad (3.7.1)$$

where s is the grid period, $n = 1, 2$ the rank of the harmonic, and PTF is evaluated at the spatial frequency of that harmonic. The bottom part of the table gives the chromaticity, i.e. the differential displacement of a B star with respect to a K star, $\Delta\eta(B) - \Delta\eta(K)$, in 10^{-3} arcsec. Each quantity is given for nine object directions (η, ζ) and at the fundamental frequency of the grid (corresponding to $s = 1.1''$) and, in parentheses, the second harmonic. MTF and PTF are averaged over the wavelength interval 300 - 600 nm, weighted by the S20-type sensitivity and the flux distribution of an F star. (The effective wavelength is 400, 450, and 475 nm for spectral type B2, F5, and K3.) Only results for the first field are given; there is a symmetry about origin so that the OTF of the other field at (η, ζ) is the complex conjugate of the present OTF at $(-\eta, -\zeta)$. (This relation does not always hold for the perturbed telescope.)

3.7.2. Degradation of OTF due to misalignment of elements

Misalignments of the optical elements generally produce a decreased MTF (although it may locally increase) and a numerically larger PTF with consequently increased chromaticity. The degradation of OTF was studied by displacing or rotating each element separately, while leaving the others at the nominal positions. Including the grid support (defining the surface where the OTF is evaluated) there are thus 24 degrees of freedom; however, one element may be taken as reference, and some of the remaining degrees of freedom do not have any effect on the OTF (for reasons of symmetry). The linear displacements $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$ around the three axes ($x =$ optical axis from primary towards complex mirror; y is along the plane through the complex mirror normals) and the rotations

Table 3.7.2. OTF of nominal instrument at the grid frequency (and second harmonic) and nine different object directions (η, ζ). Top: normalized MTF for F star. Middle: displacement $\Delta\eta(F) = (ns/2\pi)PTF$ ($n=1, 2$; $s=1.1''$; F-type star) in 10^{-3} arcsec. Bottom: chromaticity $\Delta\eta(B) - \Delta\eta(K)$ in 10^{-3} arcsec.

$\zeta \backslash \eta$	-20'.6	0	20'.6
20'.6	.451 (.304)	.447 (.302)	.395 (.261)
0	.449 (.311)	.458 (.320)	.412 (.282)
-20'.6	.430 (.283)	.451 (.303)	.421 (.281)
20'.6	40.1 (28.8)	49.9 (36.8)	54.1 (41.2)
0	-14.7 (-12.0)	- 2.0 (- 1.6)	9.5 (8.2)
-20'.6	-68.0 (-51.5)	-54.7 (-40.4)	-37.6 (-26.8)
20'.6	1.1 (1.6)	1.5 (0.6)	0.4 (-2.0)
0	-0.8 (1.1)	-0.1 (0.1)	0.2 (-1.1)
-20'.6	-2.2 (0.8)	-1.9 (-0.5)	-0.6 (-0.7)

*theory: $\lambda_{eff} = 450nm$
 $\Rightarrow$ MTF = 0.460*

$\Delta\theta$ and $\Delta\Psi$ around y and z are referenced (in the following discussion) to the primary, while the orientation of the complex mirror is taken as reference for rotation around the x axis ($\Delta\varphi$). The OTF was computed at a single wavelength, for both fields, and for the nine object directions in Table 3.7.2.

Results for the MTF (at the fundamental frequency only) are given in Table 3.7.3. Since the degradation is often very uneven across the field, the table gives for each field the worst degradation among the nine points and also the average degradation over the field.

The precision of astrometric results will be directly proportional to the MTF. We should therefore aim at an MTF not less than (say) 90 % of the MTF of the nominal telescope. The most critical element is obviously the secondary mirror, where the tolerance on Δx (defocussing) is a few μm . (Incidentally, the nominal telescope is clearly not fully optimised; e.g. the best focus is at grid position $\Delta x \simeq -10 \mu\text{m}$.)

Table 3.7.4 gives results derived from the PTF computations. $\Delta\eta_i$ are the displacements in 10^{-3} arcsec computed by means of (3.7.1) ($n=1$) for the two fields ($i=1, 2$) and different object directions. $\Delta\eta_i^0$ are the corresponding quantities for the nominal telescope. $\overline{\Delta\eta_i}$ and $\overline{\Delta\eta_i^0}$ denote field averages (over the nine directions).

Columns (3) - (4) show the maximum image displacements with respect to the nominal instrument. The quantity $\Delta\eta_i - \Delta\eta_i^0$ is of interest for an appreciation of the chromaticity, since it is generally found that the chromaticity is $\sim 3\%$ of the total image displacement (cf. Table 3.7.2). Successful calibration of the chromaticity thus imposes constraints on the variation of $\Delta\eta_i - \Delta\eta_i^0$ ($\lesssim 15$ marcsec for the entire mission).

Columns (5) - (6) give the maximum differential image displacement (distorsion), again with reference to the nominal telescope. The distorsion $(\Delta\eta_i - \overline{\Delta\eta_i}) - (\Delta\eta_i^0 - \overline{\Delta\eta_i^0})$ can be calibrated by means of the star observations themselves, provided it is constant to within ~ 1 marcsec for a period of

Table 3.7.3. Percentage degradation of MTF due to misalignment of optical components: complex mirror (CM), secondary mirror (SM) and grid.

Element	Misalignment	Degradation (worst point)		Degradation (average)	
		FOV1	FOV2	FOV1	FOV2
CM	$\Delta x = - 500 \mu\text{m}$	- 0.1%	- 0.1%	+ 0.0%	+ 0.0%
	$\Delta x = + 500 \mu\text{m}$	- 0.1	- 0.1	- 0.0	- 0.0
	$\Delta y = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	- 1.1	- 1.6	- 0.0	- 0.1
	$\Delta z = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	- 3.0	- 1.8	- 0.9	+ 0.3
	$\Delta\theta = + 200''$	- 1.4	- 3.8	+ 0.1	- 0.5
	$\Delta\psi = + 200''$	- 2.9	- 2.8	- 0.7	+ 0.1
SM	$\Delta x = - 3 \mu\text{m}$	- 8.8	- 8.8	+ 0.3	+ 0.3
	$\Delta x = - 1 \mu\text{m}$	- 2.5	- 2.5	+ 0.6	+ 0.6
	$\Delta x = + 1 \mu\text{m}$	- 3.7	- 3.7	- 1.2	- 1.2
	$\Delta x = + 3 \mu\text{m}$	- 12.6	- 12.6	- 5.0	- 5.0
	$\Delta y = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	- 0.5	- 0.2	- 0.2	+ 0.2
	$\Delta z = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	- 0.6	- 1.5	+ 0.2	- 0.2
	$\Delta\theta = + 50''$	- 14.4	- 10.9	- 2.9	- 0.0
$\Delta\psi = + 50''$	- 7.4	- 3.4	- 3.8	+ 1.4	
Grid	$\Delta x = - 15 \mu\text{m}$	- 6.1	- 6.1	+ 0.7	+ 0.7
	$\Delta x = - 5 \mu\text{m}$	- 1.7	- 1.7	+ 0.5	+ 0.5
	$\Delta x = + 5 \mu\text{m}$	- 2.8	- 2.8	- 0.8	- 0.8
	$\Delta x = + 15 \mu\text{m}$	- 8.9	- 8.9	- 3.2	- 3.2

Table 3.7.4. Image displacements (in 10^{-3} arcsec) due to misalignment of optical components. $\delta\eta_i = \Delta\eta_i - \overline{\Delta\eta}_i$.

Element (1)	Misalignment (2)	$ \Delta\eta_i - \Delta\eta_i^0 _{\max}$		$ \delta\eta_i - \delta\eta_i^0 _{\max}$		$\overline{\Delta\eta}_1 - \overline{\Delta\eta}_2$ (7)
		FOV1 (3)	FOV2 (4)	FOV1 (5)	FOV2 (6)	
CM	$\Delta x = - 500 \mu\text{m}$	-1.0	+1.0	-1.1	+1.1	+0.4
	$\Delta x = + 500 \mu\text{m}$	+1.0	-1.0	-0.7	+0.7	-0.4
	$\Delta y = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	+20.7	+20.8	-1.6	+1.5	-0.0
	$\Delta z = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	-2.1	-1.9	-1.6	-1.4	-0.0
	$\Delta\theta = + 200''$	+8.5	-8.5	+1.6	+1.7	+0.0
	$\Delta\Psi = + 200''$	+5.6	+5.5	-2.7	-2.3	+0.1
SM	$\Delta x = - 3 \mu\text{m}$	+5.2	-5.2	+3.8	-3.8	-2.1
	$\Delta x = - 1 \mu\text{m}$	+2.0	-2.0	+1.5	-1.5	-0.7
	$\Delta x = + 1 \mu\text{m}$	-2.2	+2.2	-1.8	+1.8	+0.7
	$\Delta x = + 3 \mu\text{m}$	-7.7	+7.7	-6.2	+6.2	+2.1
	$\Delta y = + 50 \mu\text{m}$	-6.6	-6.6	-1.7	-1.7	-0.0
	$\Delta z = + 50$	+2.2	+2.1	+2.0	+2.0	-0.0
	$\Delta\theta = + 50''$	+7.5	-9.7	+6.9	-8.3	-0.9
$\Delta\Psi = + 50''$	-55.1	-55.7	+6.2	+4.8	-1.4	
Grid	$\Delta x = - 15 \mu\text{m}$	+4.0	-4.0	+2.9	-2.9	-1.5
	$\Delta x = - 5 \mu\text{m}$	+1.5	-1.5	+1.1	-1.1	-0.5
	$\Delta x = + 5 \mu\text{m}$	-1.6	+1.6	-1.3	+1.3	+0.5
	$\Delta x = + 15 \mu\text{m}$	-5.3	+5.3	-4.3	+4.3	+1.5

Table 3.7.5. Tolerances and stability requirements on misalignments derived from the OTF criteria discussed in the text.

(1) Optical element	(2) Type of misalignment	(3) Absolute tolerance	(4) Maximum variation over: 2.5 yrs	(5) 30 days	(6) 3 hours
COMPLEX MIRROR	ΔX	$\pm 1000 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 1000 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 500 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 500 \mu\text{m}$
	ΔY	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$
	ΔZ	$\pm 80 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 80 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 30 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 30 \mu\text{m}$
	$\Delta\phi$	0	0	0	0
	$\Delta\theta$	$\pm 4'$	$\pm 4'$	$\pm 2'$	$\pm 2'$
	$\Delta\psi$	$\pm 5'$	$\pm 5'$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 1'$
SECONDARY MIRROR	ΔX	$\pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 1.5 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$
	ΔY	$\pm 200 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 80 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$
	ΔZ	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 25 \mu\text{m}$
	$\Delta\phi$	$\pm 5'$	$\pm 5'$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 10''$
	$\Delta\theta$	$\pm 15''$	$\pm 15''$	$\pm 5''$	$\pm 5''$
	$\Delta\psi$	$\pm 30''$	$\pm 10''$	$\pm 10''$	$\pm 10''$
GRID	ΔX	$\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 4 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 4 \mu\text{m}$
	ΔY	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$
	ΔZ	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 100 \mu\text{m}$	$\pm 10 \mu\text{m}$
	$\Delta\phi$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 10''$	$\pm 0.3''$
	$\Delta\theta$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 20''$	$\pm 10''$
	$\Delta\psi$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 1'$	$\pm 20''$	$\pm 10''$

several days (~ 30 days).

Column (7) gives the difference between the two fields of the average image displacements, $\overline{\Delta\eta_1} - \overline{\Delta\eta_2}$. This quantity represents an apparent effect on the basic angle, and is thus subject to the same stability requirement as the basic angle, ~ 1 marcsec over one or a few scans (3-5 h).

The results in Table 3.7.3-4 were used to establish tolerances and stability requirements on the misalignments of the mirrors and grid support (Table 3.7.5). The absolute tolerances in column (3) correspond to an MTF of 95 % of the MTF of the nominal telescope, in view of the further degradation to be expected from imperfections of the mirror surfaces (Section 3.7.3). The stability requirements in columns (4) - (6) correspond to the PTF criteria discussed above. An exception is the requirement $\Delta\varphi \lesssim \pm 0.3''$ in 3 hours for the orientation of the grid with respect to the complex mirror. This follows from that $\Delta\varphi$, or g_{01} in (3.6.13), cannot be calibrated on a time scale less than about 3 hours, since the same stars must be observed at different ordinates (ζ), which is done on consecutive scans.

3.7.3. Degradation of OTF due to deformation of mirrors

Few computations have been made on the effects of mirror surfaces deformations, mostly due to a lack of realistic input deformation data. However, some simple considerations allow an appreciation of tolerances, to be confirmed by detailed computations.

It is well known that small-scale, "random", wavefront errors having amplitudes much less than the wavelength of the light (λ) cause a uniform degradation of MTF (at least at spatial frequencies greater than the correlation length of the wavefront errors) according to

$$\text{MTF} = \text{MTF}^0 \exp\left[-(2\pi\delta_{\text{rms}}/\lambda)^2\right], \quad (3.7.2)$$

where δ_{rms} is the rms wavefront error. Thus, the criterion $\text{MTF} \geq 0.9 \text{MTF}^0$ corresponds to $\delta_{\text{rms}} \lesssim \lambda/19 \approx 24$ nm.

With ULE glass mirrors there is no possibility that thermal deformations amount to more than 1 - 2 nm (the temperature being controlled to a few tenths of a Kelvin), so we are mainly concerned about manufacturing imperfections. These are constant for the whole mission and their effects largely eliminated (in-flight calibration) by the scientific data processing.

The small-scale wavefront errors considered above essentially cause a non-specular reflection (scattering) of part of the incident light, which is thus removed from the centre of the point spread function out to the wings. For statistical reasons the scattering is largely symmetric, i.e. does not affect PTF appreciably. An approximate analytical treatment shows in fact that only wavefront errors having periods (in the pupil plane) of $\sim 1/3$ to $\sim 1/1$ of the pupil length (0.25 m) give rise to image displacements and chromaticity before the MTF is seriously degraded /28/. Odd (sine) distortions of the wavefront with periods $\sim 1/2$ the pupil length are the most critical.

The performance degradation due to such large-scale deformations was studied with the AML software, applying in a first experiment a deformation of the complex mirror (field 1 only)

$$\delta x = A \cos(2\pi y/L) + B \sin(2\pi y/L), \quad (3.7.3)$$

with $A = B = 5$ nm and $L = 0.125$ m. In a second experiment the secondary mirror was deformed with $A = B = 5$ nm and $L = 0.0394$ m. Projected on the entrance pupil, the amplitude ($\delta_{\text{rms}} = 10$ nm) and period (0.125 m) are identical for the two experiments. However, different parts of the secondary mirror are illuminated for different object directions, while the complex mirror is close to the entrance pupil; hence, the amplitude of the odd wavefront error component is independent of object direction for deformed complex (or primary) mirror, but is expected to depend on the object direction (along η) for deformed secondary. Results of the computations, Table 3.7.6, show the expected behaviour. Also, the average MTF degradation agrees with the - 1.9% predicted by (3.7.2). Clearly, chromaticity imposes a stricter tolerance than the MTF criterion for surface errors of these particularly critical spatial frequencies.

3.8. Accuracy analysis

The final accuracy of the astrometric parameters may be rigorously predicted from a study of the error (covariance) propagation through the adopted data processing scheme (cf. Fig. 3.6.2). What is presented below is a much simplified accuracy analysis which nevertheless takes into consideration all identified major error sources and is believed to be rather conservative.

We consider elementary observations consisting of rapid switching between two stars of magnitude m and m' , so that the integration time on each star is T and T' . We assume that a prescription exists for the total duration of the elementary observation, $\delta t = T + T'$, as a function of m and m' .

3.8.1. The mean error of a grid coordinate

Given m and T , the variance of the measured grid coordinate of the star image at the centre of the elementary observation interval, $\bar{G}$ (here expressed in arcsec for convenience), is

$$\sigma_G^2(m, T) = T^{-1} \left[\sigma_{\text{phot}}^2(m) + \sigma_j^2 + \sigma_{\text{pk}}^2 + \sigma_g^2 \right], \quad (3.8.1)$$

The terms inside the brackets are contributions (in arcsec² s) from photon statistics, residual attitude jitter, photocathode inhomogeneities, and uncalibrated grid defects, all assumed to be uncorrelated and white-noise like.

Photon noise

For the intensity model [cf. eq. (3.6.2)]

$$I(G) = i_0 + i(m) \left[1 + M_1 \cos \Psi + M_2 \cos 2\Psi \right], \quad (3.8.2)$$

where $\Psi = \psi_0 + 2\pi G/s$ and i_0 and $i(m)$ are the background and stellar count rates respectively, we have

$$[\sigma_{\text{phot}}(m)]^{-2} = \left\langle \frac{[I'(G)]^2}{I(G)} \right\rangle = \quad (3.8.3)$$

$$= \left(\frac{2\pi}{s} \right)^2 i(m) \left\langle \frac{(M_1 \sin \psi + 2M_2 \sin 2\psi)^2}{1 + i_o/i(m) + M_1 \cos \psi + M_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle$$

With usual notations, the modulation coefficient of the k:th harmonic is ($k=1, 2$)

$$M_k = \overline{\text{MTF}}_k \frac{2 \sin(k\pi \delta)}{k\pi \delta} \frac{\sin(k\pi v \Delta t/s)}{k\pi v \Delta t/s}, \quad (3.8.4)$$

where the average MTF may be taken to be 90 % of the mean values for the nominal instrument (Table 3.7.2). Inserting the numerical values

$$\overline{\text{MTF}}_1, \overline{\text{MTF}}_2 = 0.390, 0.264$$

$$s = 1.1 \text{ arcsec}$$

$$\delta = 0.25$$

$$v = 150 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta t = 1/1200 \text{ s}$$

we find

$$M_1 = 0.687$$

$$M_2 = 0.308$$

and (3.8.3) becomes

$$\sigma_{\text{phot}}^2(m) = 0.0813 \frac{1 + i_o/i(m)}{i(m)} \text{ arcsec}^2 \text{ s}. \quad (3.8.5)$$

The count rates i_o and $i(m)$ are estimated in Table 3.8.1 - 2:

$$i(m) = 1780 \text{ dex} [-0.4(m-9)] \quad \text{Hz} \quad (3.8.6)$$

$$i_o = 29 \quad \text{Hz}$$

and resulting $i(m)$ and $\sigma_{\text{phot}}(m)$ are shown in Table 3.8.3.

Table 3.8.1. Estimation of stellar count rate $i(m)$

Monochromatic stellar flux /10/, $m = B = 9.0$, $B - V = 0.5$:

. at $\lambda 300$ nm	:	$f_\lambda = 7760 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$	
. at $\lambda 400$ "	:	$f_\lambda = 31600$	"
. at $\lambda 500$ "	:	$f_\lambda = 39800$	"
. at $\lambda 600$ "	:	$f_\lambda = 38900$	"

Collecting aperture area (each field) : $A = 0.020 \text{ m}^2$

Total instrument transmittance : $T = 0.11$

- three telescope mirrors @ 0.9 : 0.73
- grid obscuration factor (δ) : 0.25
- relay optics collecting efficiency (diffraction loss) : 0.90
- transmittance of grid support and relay optics (including filter and two mirrors) : 0.70

Spectral window (interference filter) : $\lambda = 300 - 600 \text{ nm}$ FWHM

Detection efficiency :

- IDT window (UV) and photocathode quantum efficiency
 - . at $\lambda 300$ nm : $q_\lambda = 0.16$
 - . at $\lambda 400$ " : $q_\lambda = 0.20$
 - . at $\lambda 500$ " : $q_\lambda = 0.12$
 - . at $\lambda 600$ " : $q_\lambda = 0.06$
- electronic mesh transmittance : $k_c = 0.65$
- counting efficiency (discr.) : $k_e = 0.90$

Total average count rate $i(9)$ = $\int f_\lambda A T q_\lambda k_c k_e d\lambda = 1780 \text{ Hz}$

Table 3.8.2. Estimation of background count rate i_0

Sky background (Allen, Astrophysical Quantities, 1973, p. 134)
for $2 \times \text{IFOV} = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ deg}^2$ and photographic magnitudes :

- zodiacal light :	6 Hz
- faint stars :	5 Hz
- diffuse galactic light :	1 Hz

Straylight : ~ 12 Hz

Dark count rate /18, I-117/ : 5 Hz

Total background count rate $i_0 = 29$ Hz

Table 3.8.3. Number of programme stars (N), count rates $i(m)$, and various mean errors (see text for explanation) as functions of stellar magnitude m ($\simeq B$). Units: Hz and 10^{-3} arcsec.

m	N	$i(m)$	σ_{phot}	$\sigma_G(1's)$	σ_a	σ_α
< 6	3 000	> 28 200	1.7	2.6	8.4	3.4
6 - 7	5 400	17 800	2.1	2.9	8.6	3.5
7 - 8	14 800	7 090	3.4	3.9	9.1	3.7
8 - 9	40 800	2 820	5.4	5.7	10.1	4.0
9 - 10	16 000	1 120	8.6	8.8	11.8	4.6
10 - 11	12 000	447	13.9	14.0	14.5	5.7
11 - 12	6 000	178	23	23	18.9	7.4
12 - 13	2 000	71	40	40	26.7	10.5

Jitter (continuous control)

In the worst case, when the wheel frequency happens to fall in one of the spectral windows due to the IFOV switching, the rms jitter contribution to a $\delta t = 1.7$ s angle measurement is 0.45 marcsec (Section 3.3.2), corresponding to

$$\sigma_j^2 = 0.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ arcsec}^2 \text{ s.} \quad (3.8.7)$$

Photocathode inhomogeneities

The most important contribution is from small-scale random sensitivity variations (Section 3.4.2). For dwell time 0.1 s a conservative estimate is 4 marcsec rms, corresponding to

$$\sigma_{pk}^2 = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ arcsec}^2 \text{ s.} \quad (3.8.8)$$

Uncalibrated grid defects

Random errors of individual slit positions, after elimination of distortions on larger scales, may be of the order of 0.2 μm rms, corresponding to

$$\sigma_g^2 = 2.0 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ arcsec}^2 \text{ s.} \quad (3.8.9)$$

Adding (3.8.7) - (3.8.9) to $\sigma_{\text{phot}}^2(m)$ we find the grid coordinate mean errors for $T = 1$ s, $\sigma_G(m, 1 \text{ s})$, listed in Table 3.8.3.

3.8.2. Mean errors of angle measurements

The variance of the angle along the RGC between the two stars of an elementary observation is

$$\sigma_a^2(m, T; m', T') = \sigma_G^2(m, T) + \sigma_G^2(m', T') + (\zeta - \zeta')^2 \sigma_\varphi^2 \quad (3.8.10)$$

where the last term accounts for the uncertainty of the attitude component $\sin q_z d\beta_z - \cos q_z \cos \beta_z d\lambda_z$, cf. eq. (3.6.34).

Assuming uniform distribution $\zeta \in [-0.45^\circ, +0.45^\circ]$ and $\sigma_\varphi = 0.1$ arcsec, we have

$$\overline{(\zeta - \zeta')^2} \sigma_\varphi^2 = 0.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ arcsec}^2 \quad (3.8.11)$$

Given the prescription $T + T' = \delta t(m, m')$, eq. (3.8.10) is minimised by the partitioning

$$T / T' = \sigma_G(m, 1 s) / \sigma_G(m', 1 s), \quad (3.8.12)$$

yielding σ_a as a function of m and m' only:

$$\sigma_a^2(m, m') = \delta t(m, m')^{-1} \left[\sigma_G(m, 1 s) + \sigma_G(m', 1 s) \right]^2 + \overline{(\zeta - \zeta')^2} \sigma_\varphi^2. \quad (3.8.13)$$

Table 3.8.4 gives $\sigma_a(m, m')$ together with $T(m, m')$ and $T'(m, m')$ for the quite arbitrary prescription

$$\delta t(m, m') = 0.364 \left[\sigma_G(m, 1 s)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \sigma_G(m', 1 s)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right], \quad (3.8.14)$$

designed to give increased observing time to pairs containing faint stars. Eq. (3.8.14) is normalised so that the overall average time per pair, with the magnitude distribution in Table 3.8.3, is $\overline{\delta t} = 2.0$ s.

Since a particular star (m) will be observed relative to several different stars of various magnitudes (m' distributed as in Table 3.8.3), we may perform an averaging of $\sigma_a(m, m')$ over m' , yielding the average mean error per angle measurement $\sigma_a(m)$ given in Table 3.8.3.

3.8.3. Mean errors of star abscissas

The solution of a single great-circle scan in Step 1 yields the star abscissas with variance

$$\sigma_\alpha^2(m) = \frac{UN_s}{2M_s} \sigma_a^2(m) + \sigma_c^2 + \sigma_\gamma^2 \quad (3.8.15)$$

where N_s and M_s are the number of stars (abscissas) and angle

Table 3.8.4. Time partitioning T/T' and mean errors of angle

measurements of pairs (m, m'). Table gives $\frac{T(m, m')}{T'(m, m')}$ $\sigma_a(m, m')$.

Units: sec and 10^{-3} arcsec.

$m' \backslash m$	< 6	6 - 7	7 - 8	8 - 9	9 - 10	10 - 11	11 - 12	12 - 13
< 6	$\frac{0.58}{0.58}$ 4.8	$\frac{0.63}{0.57}$ 5.0	$\frac{0.78}{0.52}$ 5.7	$\frac{1.00}{0.45}$ 6.9	$\frac{1.29}{0.37}$ 8.9	$\frac{1.65}{0.30}$ 11.9	$\frac{2.10}{0.23}$ 16.8	$\frac{2.72}{0.17}$ 25.2
6 - 7	$\frac{0.57}{0.63}$ 5.0	$\frac{0.62}{0.62}$ 5.2	$\frac{0.77}{0.57}$ 5.9	$\frac{0.99}{0.50}$ 7.1	$\frac{1.28}{0.42}$ 9.0	$\frac{1.65}{0.34}$ 12.0	$\frac{2.11}{0.26}$ 16.9	$\frac{2.73}{0.20}$ 25.2
7 - 8	$\frac{0.52}{0.78}$ 5.7	$\frac{0.57}{0.77}$ 5.9	$\frac{0.72}{0.72}$ 6.5	$\frac{0.95}{0.64}$ 7.7	$\frac{1.25}{0.55}$ 9.5	$\frac{1.64}{0.45}$ 12.4	$\frac{2.11}{0.36}$ 17.2	$\frac{2.76}{0.27}$ 25.3
8 - 9	$\frac{0.45}{1.00}$ 6.9	$\frac{0.50}{0.99}$ 7.1	$\frac{0.64}{0.95}$ 7.7	$\frac{0.87}{0.87}$ 8.7	$\frac{1.18}{0.77}$ 10.5	$\frac{1.59}{0.65}$ 13.2	$\frac{2.10}{0.52}$ 17.8	$\frac{2.78}{0.40}$ 25.8
9 - 10	$\frac{0.37}{1.29}$ 8.9	$\frac{0.42}{1.28}$ 9.0	$\frac{0.55}{1.25}$ 9.5	$\frac{0.77}{1.18}$ 10.5	$\frac{1.08}{1.08}$ 12.0	$\frac{1.50}{0.95}$ 14.6	$\frac{2.05}{0.78}$ 19.0	$\frac{2.78}{0.61}$ 26.6
10 - 11	$\frac{0.30}{1.65}$ 11.9	$\frac{0.34}{1.65}$ 12.0	$\frac{0.45}{1.64}$ 12.4	$\frac{0.65}{1.59}$ 13.2	$\frac{0.95}{1.50}$ 14.6	$\frac{1.37}{1.37}$ 17.0	$\frac{1.94}{1.18}$ 21.0	$\frac{2.73}{0.95}$ 28.3
11 - 12	$\frac{0.23}{2.10}$ 16.8	$\frac{0.26}{2.11}$ 16.9	$\frac{0.36}{2.11}$ 17.2	$\frac{0.52}{2.10}$ 17.8	$\frac{0.78}{2.05}$ 19.0	$\frac{1.18}{1.94}$ 21.0	$\frac{1.75}{1.75}$ 24.7	$\frac{2.58}{1.48}$ 31.4
12 - 13	$\frac{0.17}{2.72}$ 25.2	$\frac{0.20}{2.73}$ 25.2	$\frac{0.27}{2.76}$ 25.3	$\frac{0.40}{2.78}$ 25.8	$\frac{0.61}{2.78}$ 26.6	$\frac{0.95}{2.73}$ 28.3	$\frac{1.48}{2.58}$ 31.4	$\frac{2.31}{2.31}$ 37.4
Average	$\frac{0.42}{1.16}$ 8.4	$\frac{0.47}{1.15}$ 8.6	$\frac{0.60}{1.12}$ 9.1	$\frac{0.82}{1.05}$ 10.1	$\frac{1.12}{0.96}$ 11.8	$\frac{1.52}{0.85}$ 14.5	$\frac{2.04}{0.71}$ 18.9	$\frac{2.75}{0.57}$ 26.7

measurements involved in the scan solution, U is a coefficient related to the "rigidity" of the solution, and σ_c and σ_γ are mean errors associated with residual chromaticity and basic angle fluctuations. It is assumed that the magnitude dependence of σ_a is directly transferred to σ_α (yet to be verified by numerical experiments).

The number U , which ideally should be unity (viz. for 360° FOV and infinitely complex IFOV switching, leading to uncorrelated normal equations), is found to be $U = 1.7$ in realistic cases (numerical experiments). With $\overline{\delta t} = 2$ s and 2.4 h scan period we have $M_s = 4320$. Furthermore, $N_s = 785$ for 0.9° FOV width. σ_c and σ_γ are both of the order of 0.5 marcsec. Eq. (3.8.15) then gives the abscissa mean errors (per scan) $\sigma_\alpha(m)$ in Table 3.8.3.

3.8.4. Mean errors of astrometric parameters

The mean errors of the astrometric parameters are obtained by applying the coefficients of improvement (Step 3) $F_\beta(\beta, \lambda)$, which are functions of position on sky (mainly of β) and of the scanning law (mainly ξ) and total mission length. Results must be corrected for fractional observation dead time f :

$$\sigma_\beta(m, \beta, \lambda) = \sigma_\alpha(m) F_\beta(\beta, \lambda) (1-f)^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (3.8.16)$$

and similarly for the other parameters $\lambda, \mu_\beta, \mu_\lambda, \omega$.

For nominal mission length 2.5 y and $\xi = 36^\circ$ the sky averages of the coefficients of improvement are /12/:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} F_\beta = 0.167 \\ F_{\lambda \cos \beta} = 0.238 \\ F_{\mu_\beta} = 0.231 \\ F_{\mu_\lambda \cos \beta} = 0.337 \\ F_\omega = 0.291 \end{array} \right\} \begin{array}{l} F_{\text{pos}} = 0.203 \\ F_{\text{p.m.}} = 0.284 \end{array}$$

NB. These factors are 10-17% larger than actually for Vaghi /19/

A conservative estimation of the fractional dead time yields:

- earth and moon occultations (Section 3.2.4) :	6 %
- eclipses :	1 %
- margin (tests, calibrations, failure) :	10 %

total fractional dead time : f = 17 %

It is estimated that the resulting average mean errors are uncertain to ± 30 %. Consequently, they are multiplied by a further factor 1.3 to give a safe margin.

The final results are given in Table 3.8.5.

Table 3.8.5. Estimated mean errors of astrometric parameters in 10^{-3} arcsec.

m_{pg}	N	complete- ness	observing time		mean errors (sky averages)		
					pos.	p.m.	par.
< 6	3 000	100 %	270 s	1 %	1.0	1.4	1.4
6 - 7	5 400	100	310	3	1.0	1.4	1.4
7 - 8	14 800	100	390	9	1.1	1.5	1.5
8 - 9	40 800	100	530	33	1.2	1.6	1.7
9 - 10	16 000	15	730	18	1.3	1.9	1.9
10 - 11	12 000	4	990	18	1.7	2.3	2.4
11 - 12	6 000	0.8	1330	12	2.2	3.0	3.1
12 - 13	2 000	0.1	1780	6	3.0	4.3	4.3
Total	100 000		$65 \cdot 10^6$ s	100 %			
Average			650 s		1.3	1.8	1.9

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(An exhaustive list of pertinent references up to March 1978 is found in /11/.)

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